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California State University, Fullerton
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INCREASING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN CHILDREN WITH ASTHMA: A FAMILY AND
COMMUNITY APPROACH

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

In the U.S., approximately 4.7 million children (6.5%) are affected by asthma, while obesity impacts approximately 14.7 million children (19.7%). Children with asthma, particularly underserved minority children living in urban communities, face an increased risk of obesity and subsequently worse health outcomes than their non-obese asthmatic peers. One reason is that these children have lower physical activity levels than their non-asthmatic peers. This evidence-based Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was designed to evaluate the effectiveness of a community-based, family-centered education program for parents of school-aged children with asthma. The project aimed to increase parental understanding of the importance of physical activity for children with asthma, thereby reducing obesity risk. Using a pre-test/post-test design, this project explored: a) demographic characteristics, b) asthma and physical activity characteristics, c) knowledge, perceptions, and beliefs, and d) community needs and barriers among the participants. Nine Hispanic/Latino parents of children with asthma (ages 6-10) participated in this project. Seventy-five percent of the parents reported that their children experience asthma trouble during exercise, while 62.5% of parents reported that their children utilized albuterol after exercise. No statistically significant differences across survey components were observed between pre-and post-intervention groups. Despite this, there was a notable positive shift in perceptions regarding the relationship between physical activity and asthma. Three out of eight participants (37.5%) transitioned from being undecided to agreeing or strongly agreeing that physical activity may improve a child's asthma. Initially, 56% of the parents expressed fear that their child would become ill due to physical activity, exercise, or sports. However, post-intervention, significant positive shifts in perceptions were observed in four (50%) of the participants. Five out of nine participants (56%) of the participants initially agreed that "There is not enough time in the day for physical activity." Post-intervention three out of eight participants (37.5%) positively shifted from "agree" pre-intervention to "disagree." This DNP project offers insights into the challenges faced by a small sample Hispanic/Latino parent of children with asthma. The findings in this project suggests that educating parents about the significance of physical activity for their children could potentially shift their perceptions, potentially leading to positive changes in behavior and attitudes toward physical activity in children with asthma. This educational intervention could potentially lead to increased physical activity, improved exercise induced asthma management, and overall reduced risk of obesity in these high-risk children.

Keywords: obesity, asthma, physical activity, children, community-based, family-centered interventions, Hispanic/Latino, urban communities, social determinants of health

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Background

In the United States, approximately 4.7 million children (6.5%) are affected by asthma, while obesity impacts approximately 14.7 million children (19.7%) (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2023; Stierman et al., 2021). Alarming, children with asthma face an increased risk of obesity and subsequently worse health outcomes than their non-obese asthmatic peers (CDC, 2022a; Chen et al., 2017; Holderness et al., 2017; Stratakis et al., 2022; Zang et al., 2018). Children with asthma have a 37% to 51% higher risk of becoming obese (Chen et al., 2017; Zang et al., 2018). Children with asthma and obesity report more daytime symptoms, physical activity limitations, and frequently missed school days (Wiesenthal et al., 2016). These children are also more likely to go to the emergency department (ED) or be hospitalized than their normal-weight peers (Manion & Velsor-Friedrich, 2017).

Asthma and obesity both have significant healthcare and financial burdens. An estimated \$82 billion is spent annually on asthma-related costs, including medical expenditures, ED visits, missed school, and missed parent or caregiver workdays (Nurmagambetov et al., 2018). Children with asthma account for twice as many ED and urgent care visits (17.9%) than adults (10.1%) (Pate et al., 2021). In 2019, children with asthma accounted for approximately 790,478 ED visits and 64,255 hospitalizations (CDC, 2023). Reducing asthma attacks, ED visits, and hospitalizations in children with asthma are Healthy People 2030 objectives (United States Department of Health and Human Services [USDHHS], n.d.-b). Remarkably, obesity costs the US healthcare system \$173 billion annually (CDC, 2022a). Obesity is associated with a risk for other chronic medical conditions, including asthma, type 2 diabetes mellitus, and cardiovascular disease, contributing to the healthcare system's financial burden (CDC, 2022a). Reducing the proportion of children with obesity is also a focus of the Healthy People 2030 objectives

(USDHHS, n.d.-a). A diagnosis of both asthma and obesity is a burden on the child, their family, and the healthcare system. Therefore, reducing the risk of obesity in children with asthma is crucial to decreasing asthma morbidity.

Racial and ethnic disparities exist in asthma and obesity, and social determinants of health (SDOH) play a significant role in health outcomes for these comorbidities. Among all ages, asthma is highest among the non-Hispanic Black population (10.7%) and those of Hispanic Puerto Rican descent (14.0%) (Pate et al., 2021). Black and Hispanic children and those insured by the Children's Health Insurance Program (CHIP) are more likely to visit an ED for asthma (Pate et al., 2021). Obesity prevalence is highest among Hispanic (26.2%) and non-Hispanic Black (24.8%) children and adolescents (Stierman et al., 2021). Furthermore, asthma and obesity are more common among low-income families (Pate et al., 2021; Stierman et al., 2021). In persons with family incomes <100% of the federal poverty level (FPL), asthma is more prevalent (11.4%) than in families with higher incomes (Pate et al., 2021). In all children with obesity, prevalence decreases with increasing family income (Stierman et al., 2021).

Obesity and asthma are comorbidities that disproportionately affect underserved children in urban communities (Holderness et al., 2017). Underserved communities, which include members of minority populations, lack adequate access to medical care and experience health disparities (USDHHS, n.d.-c) and are similar to disadvantaged communities, which suffer from economic, health, and environmental burdens throughout California (State of California, 2024). The Orange County Children's Partnership (2022) acknowledges that socioeconomic status (SES) encompasses income, education, occupation, and social standing relative to others. For children, SES typically involves family income, parental education, and parental occupation, along with self-reported perceptions of social status and quality of life. These SES factors

reliably predict various health outcomes in children and adolescents. These factors are influenced by individual characteristics, including behaviors like diet and physical activity and environmental factors such as their neighborhood, all of which interact to contribute to disparities (Orange County Children's Partnership, 2022). Socioeconomically disadvantaged students are defined as those eligible for the free or reduced-price meal (FRPM) program, as well as those who belong to migrant families, are homeless, live in foster care, or whose parents did not graduate from high school (California Department of Education, 2023).

According to Holderness et al. (2017), underserved children in urban communities have been found to have lower physical activity levels than their non-asthmatic peers and are at greater risk of being overweight or obese. Underserved children with obesity and asthma in urban communities experience limited physical activity opportunities influenced by several factors: 1) parental concerns about asthma symptoms that could be triggered by exercise, 2) inadequate physical activity options in schools, communities, and neighborhoods, and 3) safety concerns in their neighborhoods lead parents to keep their children indoors, resulting in sedentary behavior (Eisenberg et al., 2020; Islamovic et al., 2019; Holderness et al., 2017; Kornblit et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2017).

The literature recommends increasing physical activity in children with asthma, including culturally appropriate family-centered approaches and interventions (Eisenberg et al., 2020; Islamovic et al., 2019; Jago et al., 2017; Kornblit et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2017). Family-centered interventions combine activities to build family support with health education to increase physical activity among children (Community Preventive Services Task Force [CPSTF], 2017). These interventions are designed to enhance communication and unity by utilizing goal-setting tools, positive reinforcement of health behaviors organized physical activity sessions, and

providing information on other lifestyle behaviors such as healthy eating and screen time reduction (CPSTF, 2017). Educating both child and parent on the benefits of regular physical activity and how to prevent exercise-induced symptoms should be included. Family-based interventions are more effective in achieving and sustaining the child's body mass index (BMI) reduction than interventions that target the child without including the family, for example, school-based interventions (Hampl et al., 2023). Therefore, parent participation can be critical to a successful obesity prevention program. Additionally, other research has shown that community partnerships can help remove barriers to physical activity (Kornblit et al., 2018). An intervention that provides education on physical activity and its relationship with improved asthma management can reduce the risk of obesity in children with asthma (Reddel et al., 2021).

Problem Statement

The Wellness on Wheels (WoW) is an asthma and community outreach program and the only asthma mobile clinic in Orange County (O.C.), a region in Southern California. WoW has provided care for underserved children with asthma and their families since it was founded in 2002. In recent years, WoW has observed a surge in obesity rates among children with asthma, closely paralleling the alarming trend of rising obesity rates among children residing in O.C. where between 2018 and 2019, the proportion of O.C. students who were overweight or obese increased by 0.3 and 0.6 percentage points respectively (The Orange County Community Indicators Team, 2020). A data report pulled from WoW's electronic health record showed that in 2022, the program provided care for over 800 predominantly Hispanic children with asthma, and 50% of these children were overweight or obese. At the time of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Project, WoW had no curriculum that addressed obesity prevention in these children with asthma.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this evidenced-based DNP project was to evaluate the effectiveness of a community-based, family-centered education program for parents of school-aged children with asthma. The project aimed to increase parental understanding of the importance of physical activity for children with asthma and encourage the family to develop goals that included incorporating physical activity to their lifestyle. The educational session was presented in a community resource center to expose parents to a safe environment for families to be physically active. Increased understanding of the importance of physical activity for their children with asthma can reduce the risk of obesity.

Supporting Framework – Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

Advanced Practice Nurses use evidence-based practice (EBP) to integrate the best research evidence with clinical practice (Grove & Gray, 2019). The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care (Appendix A, Figure 1) is a validated tool for EBP that has been used since 2001 and was recently revised and improved in 2017 (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). Permission was granted to use the Iowa model as the supporting framework (Appendix B) to guide this DNP project in implementing research evidence into clinical practice (Appendix C, Figure 2).

This framework uses systematic multi-steps with decision points to evaluate and modify the steps if needed based on the collected evidence (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The Iowa Model has been used to implement the Asthma Control Test (ACT) screening tool into primary care practice to improve asthma management (Banasiak, 2018). It has also been used for postpartum depression (PPD) screening in a multilingual, low socioeconomic-status urban population and trauma-informed care of children and adolescents in an inpatient psychiatric

setting (Cohen et al., 2022; Hale & Wendler, 2023). Trauma-informed care addresses the signs, symptoms, and effects of trauma on patients to provide better support for patients' healthcare needs (State of California Department of Health Care Services [DHCS], 2024d).

The Iowa Model (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017) contains ten systematic steps, including three decision points that guided this DNP project. The first step entailed identifying the triggers for the project. The trigger can be patient- or clinic-focused. The patient-focused trigger for this DNP project was the increased obesity rates in children with asthma. In 2022, Wellness on Wheels (WoW) provided care for over 800 children with asthma, and data showed that 50% of these children were overweight or obese.

The second step in this model involved stating the question or purpose of the project. This DNP project aimed to create an educational program for parents and caregivers of school-aged, underserved children with asthma. This program aimed to increase knowledge, change parental perceptions of exercise and asthma, increase physical activity in children and families, and connect families to physical activity opportunities in their local community.

The third step, the first decision point in this model, identified the issue as a priority to WoW as revealed by a community health insight survey (Appendix D) indicating 59% of respondents would like further support or education about physical wellness (National Research Corporation [NRC], 2022). In addition, WoW envisions a community-based program promoting community engagement, family resilience, and well-being. Subsequently a team was formed in the fourth step. The Iowa Model supports gathering multidisciplinary perspectives on the problem being addressed. The project team included a principal investigator (the author of this project), the WoW program supervisor, and the Community Center supervisors from each site.

The fifth step entailed performing a literature review and synthesis of high-level evidence supporting the topic. The literature review was aimed to find research that supported the need to address the patient-focused triggers and identify evidence-based solutions. For this DNP project, a literature search was conducted to identify evidence concerning obesity and physical activity in school-aged children with asthma. The research was synthesized in the literature section review of this proposal. This led to the sixth step, which was the second decision point to answer if sufficient research evidence supported this project. Because sufficient evidence was found, the seventh step comprised the design and pilot of the intervention or practice change. The DNP project objectives for the education program were developed in this step based on evidence in the literature. Questionnaires for baseline and post-intervention data collection were developed and adapted from the literature.

The eighth step was the third decision point, where the intervention was evaluated for appropriate adoption into practice. The author of this DNP project identified implications for clinical practice and recommendations for improving the educational program's success. The final two steps will be integrating and sustaining the intervention into practice and disseminating the intervention, which may go beyond the timeline for this DNP project. The author of this evidence-based project plans to disseminate the findings to the organization and other stakeholders with a poster board, oral presentation, and scholarly paper. In these final steps, WoW may build on this DNP project and eventually include children and their parents as participants during these educational sessions.

Review of the Literature

A literature review was completed to find research that supports the need to address the patient problem and identify evidence-based solutions for this DNP project. The purpose of the

literature review is to present and summarize the current knowledge on the topic addressed by this DNP project (Grove & Gray, 2019).

Search Strategy

A literature search was conducted to identify evidence concerning obesity in children with asthma and how physical activity affects both health conditions. Key terms “obesity,” “asthma,” “physical activity,” and “children” were searched for in CINAHL, Google Scholar, PubMed, and ScienceDirect databases. Filters were applied to ensure the results produced articles from peer-reviewed journals in English and within the last six years, from 2016 to 2023. Articles that included studies only on “adolescents” or “adults” were excluded. Greater than 200 articles met this inclusion criteria. Therefore, another in-depth search included key terms “urban communities,” “community-based,” and “family-centered care” decreased the total to less than 40 articles. Articles that included all three key terms of “obesity,” “asthma,” and “physical activity” were the first articles that were reviewed and synthesized. In addition, articles written in the last six years that were repeatedly cited in systematic reviews or meta-analyses about the patient problem were included in this review.

This literature review includes the most up-to-date research on the key concepts of asthma, obesity, and physical activity in children. Most importantly, the literature review highlighted the relationship between these three concepts. The literature review also includes how family and community-centered care is essential to implementing successful interventions for children with asthma and obesity. A total of approximately 25 articles were found to be relevant to this literature review.

Asthma in Children

Globally, asthma is the most common chronic disease among all children (World Health Organization [WHO], 2024). This chronic condition causes inflammation and narrowing of the muscles around the airways in the lungs, which results in symptoms of coughing, wheezing, chest tightness, and shortness of breath (National Heart, Lungs, and Blood Institute [NHLBI], 2022b). Fortunately, evidence-based guidelines are available for managing asthma in children (Reddel et al., 2021). Asthma education includes the use of medications, trigger avoidance, and symptom management (Reddel et al., 2021; WHO, 2024). WHO (2024) emphasizes the importance of education and community awareness to reduce negative perceptions associated with asthma, especially in high-risk communities.

Asthma Risk Factors

Children with family members with asthma, especially a parent or sibling, are at a higher risk of developing asthma (NHLBI, 2022a). Other risk factors include viral infections, allergic conditions such as eczema or rhinitis, and exposure to tobacco smoking (NHLBI, 2022a; WHO, 2024). Children living in urban communities have an increased prevalence of asthma linked to various lifestyle factors, including decreased physical activity (WHO, 2024). Most significantly, being overweight or obese has been linked to the risk of developing asthma or having poor asthma control (CDC, 2022a; Chen et al., 2017; Holderness et al., 2017; NHLBI, 2022a; Stratakis et al., 2022; WHO, 2024; Zang et al., 2018).

Asthma Prevalence in Local Communities

Active lifetime prevalence refers to a diagnosis of asthma at one point by a healthcare provider (California Department of Public Health [CDPH], 2022b). In California, the asthma lifetime prevalence for children ages 0 to 17 years is 11.9%, and in O.C., it is 13.8%. Active

asthma prevalence, which represents a current diagnosis of asthma in children, stands at 7.4% in California and 8.4% in O.C. (CDPH, 2022b). Asthma disproportionately affects low-income and minority children. Black and Hispanic Latino children are twice as likely to have asthma and suffer from severe asthma than white children (CDPH, 2022a). Black children are six times more likely than white children to visit the ED due to asthma, while Hispanic and Latino children are twice as likely to go to the ED (CDPH, 2022a). CDPH (2022a) has concluded that poor access to quality healthcare, healthier food choices, and safe and affordable housing have all contributed to health inequities in children with asthma.

WoW serves children with asthma who receive Medi-Cal, California's Medicaid program. This a public health insurance program that provides healthcare services to low-income individuals including children (DHCS, n.d.). These demographics align with national findings, where asthma is more prevalent among persons with lower family incomes (Pate et al., 2021). In 2022, approximately 83% of WoW patients were between the ages of 5 to 17 years, with more than half between ages 5 to 12 years. In that same year, greater than half of the patients were Hispanic or Latino with Spanish-speaking parents or caregivers.

Physical Activity in Children

Physical activity is any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that requires energy expenditure and often refers to movements done in leisure or sports (CDC, 2017). Regular physical activity is associated with positive health outcomes and decreases risk factors for coronary heart disease, type two diabetes, and obesity. Physical activity especially benefits individuals with chronic medical conditions, including asthma (USDHHS, 2018).

Two youth surveillance systems monitor progress toward the Healthy People 2030 physical activity objectives for children and adolescents (Chen et al., 2021). Children ages 6 to

13 years are monitored by the National Survey of Children's Health (NSCH), and children ages 14 to 18 years are monitored by Youth Risk Behavior Survey (YRBS). According to Chen et. al. (2021) between 2015 and 2017, only 23% of youth aged 6 to 17 years met the aerobic physical activity guideline. However, significantly more children aged 6 to 13 years (26%) met the guideline than youth aged 14 to 17 years (17%) (Chen et al., 2021). This clearly demonstrates that children are not meeting the recommended guidelines for physical activity, and interventions are needed to promote increased physical activity.

Guidelines and Recommendations

According to *The Physical Activity Guidelines for Americans* (USDHHS, 2018), children and adolescents ages 6 to 17 years should do one hour or more of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity daily, which includes aerobic, muscle-strengthening, and bone-strengthening activity on at least three days a week. The goal of aerobic physical activity is for children to continuously move their large muscles, by running, hopping, skipping, jumping rope, swimming, bicycling, and dancing. Muscle strengthening, whether structured or part of playtime, encompasses resistance games or exercises such as tug of war, climbing up a rope, playing on playground equipment, or using resistance bands. While bone strengthening exercises should produce a force on the body's bones, which includes running, hopscotch, jumping rope, and sports that involve running (USDHHS, 2018).

The Exercise is Medicine (EIM) is a global initiative by the American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM) with the goal of making physical activity assessment and exercise prescription a standard model for disease prevention and management for all patients (ACSM, 2021a). The ACSM recommends that healthcare professionals address physical activity for

patients with asthma and in children of all ages (ACSM, 2021b). The content from the ACSM aligns with *The Physical Activity Guidelines for Americans* (USDHHS, 2018).

Family-based interventions to increase physical activity among children is recommended by CPSTF (2017). These recommendations are based on a systematic review and meta-analysis of 47 studies by Brown et al. (2016). Brown et al. (2016) concluded that family-based interventions to promote physical activity in children have been effective and 66% had positive effects on physical activity. However, Brown et al. (2016) found that parents lacked an understanding of how to change a child's physical activity behavior and were unsure of the resources that were available to help promote a child's physical activity. Interventions tailored to ethnic and cultural perspectives were well-received. However, a lack of family support was found to restrict healthy behavior changes in children.

While Brown et al. (2016) concluded that providing parental education is an effective intervention for changing physical activity knowledge, education alone was insufficient in changing behaviors. Almost half of the studies in the meta-analysis included less than 60 participants, and most (70%) included families with children ages 8 to 11 years (Brown et al., 2016). Approximately 85% of the studies included short-term post-intervention follow-up (≤ 3 months), and 30% had long-term follow-up (≥ 12 months). In more than half of the studies (53%), researchers assessed physical activity using subjective methods such as questionnaires, patient diaries, and interviews. A smaller proportion (46%) of studies used objective methods, such as pedometry, accelerometry, and/or direct observation.

Family-based interventions should actively engage families by combining activities with health education and building family support (CPSTF, 2017). These interventions can include a

combination of goal setting, reinforced positive health behaviors, organized physical activity, and education about other lifestyle behaviors, such as screen time or nutrition.

Physical Activity in Children with Asthma

Exercise and physical activity are common triggers of asthma symptoms for patients. The symptoms may be mild or severe but can be a frightening experience for children and their parents and as a result, physical activity is avoided or limited (Eisenberg et al., 2020; Islamovic et al., 2019; Koinis-Mitchell et al., 2021; Kornblit et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2017). Therefore, it is essential to clearly understand that children with asthma have distinctly unique experiences with physical activity than those of their peers who do not have asthma. This section of the literature review examines exercise-induced bronchoconstriction (EIB) and its management, as well as the benefits and barriers to physical activity in children with asthma.

Exercise-Induced Bronchoconstriction

Exercise-induced bronchoconstriction (EIB), more commonly known as exercise-induced asthma (EIA), is defined as airway narrowing or obstruction of airflow in the lungs that is reversible and is associated with physical activity and exercise (American College of Allergy, Asthma, and Immunology [ACAAI], 2021). In most up-to-date literature, EIB is the preferred term because although most asthmatic people of all ages have EIB, not all patients with EIB have asthma (ACAAI, 2021; Aggarwal et al., 2018; Reddel et al., 2021). The prevalence of EIB is about 10% to 20% of the general population, including athletes, and 40% to 90% of children and adults diagnosed with asthma (Aggarwal et al., 2018). The prevalence of EIB is also higher in children than in the general population, ranging from 3% to 35% in non-asthmatic and 40% to 90% of asthmatic children, especially in those with severe asthma or uncontrolled asthma (Aggarwal et al., 2018; Lang, 2019).

In EIB, asthma symptoms typically occur within a few minutes of starting physical activity and can last up to 15 minutes or more after stopping (ACAAI, 2021). However, there are ways to control these symptoms as part of a person's asthma management plan. The most common intervention is using a short-acting inhaled beta-2-agonist inhaler (bronchodilator) to prevent EIB or improve EIB symptoms immediately (ACAAI, 2021; National Asthma Education and Prevention Program [NAEPP], 2007; Reddel et al., 2021). Patients are instructed to use a bronchodilator as prescribed 5 to 15 minutes prior to planned physical activity. If symptoms are not relieved with a bronchodilator, then a daily inhaled corticosteroid is often added to the treatment regimen. This medication regimen usually results in a decrease in exercise related asthma symptoms. However, if a patient continues to have breakthrough EIB it may indicate poorly controlled asthma (Reddel et al., 2021).

The provider needs to understand the pathophysiology of EIB in order to provide the necessary interventions of symptom management. Providing education to the family regarding EIB and how to manage symptoms while still promoting physical activity is an essential component of this DNP project. Parents need to understand that routine physical activity and exercise in their children with asthma is safe and improves aerobic fitness, quality of life, and pulmonary function (Abdelbasset et al., 2018; Lang et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2020). Therefore, routine asthma management should include physical activity recommendations and guidelines along with the management of EIB.

Benefits of Physical Activity

Regular physical activity has multiple benefits for all children. Physically active children aged 6 to 13 years have improved cognitive function, including memory, attention, executive function, and academic performance (USDHHS, 2018). Physical activity also increases

cardiorespiratory fitness, improves muscle and bone strength, and lowers body fat. Physically active children also experience positive mental health effects, such as reduced symptoms of depression (USDHHS, 2018).

Aerobic physical activity improves pulmonary function, aerobic capacity, and quality of life in school-aged children with asthma (Abdelbasset et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2020). Abdelbasset et al. (2018) found that aerobic exercise had statistically significant benefits on pulmonary function, aerobic capacity, and pediatric quality of life in school-aged children (8 to 12 years) with asthma. In a systematic review and meta-analysis, Wu et al. (2020) found that aerobic physical activity in children and adults significantly improved pulmonary function, including forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1), forced vital capacity (FVC), and forced vital capacity (FVC)/predicted, all values that look at asthma control (NAEPP, 2007). However, there were no significant improvements in FEV1% pred and FEV1/FVC%. Wu et al. (2020) also found significant improvement in pediatric and adult quality of life; in addition, swimming and indoor treadmill were types of physical activity favorable to children with asthma.

Sanz-Santiago et al. (2020) did not find significant differences in lung function, asthma control, or quality of life between the control and intervention groups in their randomized control trial. However, they found that combined exercise training (resistance and aerobic) improved cardiorespiratory fitness and muscle strength in children and adolescents ages 7 to 17 years.

Barriers to Physical Activity

Studies have found that physical activity levels in children with asthma are lower than their non-asthmatic peers and are below the recommended guidelines, especially in urban communities (Bhagat et al., 2019; Koinis-Mitchell et al., 2021). Parental perceptions of neighborhood safety and fear of asthma symptoms are associated with decreased physical

activity (Holderness et al., 2017; Koinis-Mitchell et al., 2021; Kornblit et al., 2018; Leinaar et al., 2016). Five studies that took place in urban communities found that parents of children with asthma experience fear of asthma symptoms triggered by exercise, resulting in limited physical activity levels (Eisenberg et al., 2020; Islamovic et al., 2019; Koinis-Mitchell et al., 2021; Kornblit et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2017). All five studies included samples of Hispanic/Latino asthmatic children between the ages of 7 and 14 years and their parents. These studies are highly relevant given that the target population of this DNP project is comprised predominantly of Hispanic/Latino families.

Eisenberg et al. (2020) examined asthma outcomes and caregivers' fears about asthma and exercise while exploring the differences between normal and overweight children with asthma. Parents completed a five-point Likert-type scale questionnaire to measure parental fear of asthma and perception of exercise as a trigger for asthma. Eisenberg et al. (2020) found that 38% of parents had fears due to asthma diagnosis, 41% feared death due to asthma, and 31% feared death due to exercise-induced asthma. However, the researchers did not find a statistical difference between the association of fears and weight, which may have been due to the elevated levels of fears at baseline. Overall, Latino parents reported higher levels of fear of asthma, fear of death due to asthma, or fear of death while exercising.

Culture and peer influences may play a significant role in how Hispanic children develop perceptions and behaviors related to exercise (Shaw et al. 2017; Eisenberg et al. 2020). Barriers to physical activity, including caregiver fears about asthma and misperceptions of physical activity, should be addressed with children with asthma and their parents as part of routine asthma care and education (Eisenberg et al., 2020; Islamovic et al., 2019; Kornblit et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2017).

Reis et al. (2020) found that children (ages 6 to 11 years) whose parents did not feel safe in their neighborhoods had a risk of obesity 2.23 times greater than those who reported their neighborhoods as safe. Healthcare providers must also be aware of community barriers and consider community partnerships to remove barriers to physical activity.

Studies by Eisenberg et al., (2020); Islamovic et al., (2019); Kornblit et al., (2018); and Shaw et al., (2017) conclude that interventions should include educating both child and parent on the benefits of regular physical activity and how to prevent exercise-induced symptoms. Additionally, Kornblit et al. (2018) concluded that involving schools and community partners, would help improve physical activity levels in children with asthma. These approaches in asthma education may improve physical activity levels and decrease the risk of being overweight or obese in urban children with asthma.

Social Determinants of Health (SDOH)

Obesity and asthma are comorbidities that disproportionately affect underserved children in urban communities (Holderness et al., 2017) and may be influenced by social determinants of health. Besides decreased access to quality healthcare, underserved communities also face challenges in accessing “safe housing, transportation, nutritious food options, and physical health opportunities” (CDC, 2022b).

The Orange County Children’s Partnership (2022) acknowledges that socioeconomic status (SES) encompasses income, education, occupation, and social standing relative to others. For children, SES typically involves family income, parental education, and parental occupation, along with self-reported perceptions of social status and quality of life. These SES factors reliably predict various health outcomes in children and adolescents. These factors are influenced by individual characteristics including behaviors like diet and physical activity and

environmental factors such as their neighborhood, all of which interact to contribute to disparities (Orange County Children's Partnership, 2022). Socioeconomically disadvantaged students are defined as those eligible for the free or reduced-price meal (FRPM) program, as well as those who belong to migrant families, are homeless, live in foster care, or whose parents did not graduate from high school (California Department of Education, 2023).

Obesity in School-Aged Children

Obesity is a complex health condition based on the body's increased fat cells (CDC, 2022; NHLBI, 2022c). The body mass index (BMI) is used to screen for obesity in children. BMI is a measure of body fat based on height and weight and is age and sex specific. It is calculated by an individual's weight in kilograms divided by the square of their height in meters (CDC, 2022a). According to the CDC (2022a), a healthy weight in children is a BMI between the 5th and 85th percentile. Children with a BMI between the 85th percentile and the 95th percentile are classified as overweight, and children with a BMI in the 95th percentile or greater are obese.

Obesity Risk Factors

Obesity is caused by many factors, including lifestyle and behaviors like eating patterns, lack of sleep or physical activity, some medicines, genetics, and family history (NHLBI, 2022c). Obesity in children increases the risk of heart disease, type 2 diabetes, and mental health issues such as anxiety and depression (NHLBI, 2022c). However, the increase in childhood obesity in the last decade has been linked to unhealthy lifestyles and behaviors, as well as the community in which the child lives (Saelens et al., 2018).

The neighborhood or community may impact the family's ability to make healthy food choices which may not be easily accessible or affordable. The child may also have limited

physical activity opportunities outside of their school environment. In a prospective observational study of children ages six to 12 years, Saelens et al. (2018) found that children living in neighborhoods with increased access to walkable and recreational supportive environments and better nutritional sources, were nearly 50% less likely to be overweight or obese due to resulting in better weight outcomes and associated behavioral changes of the children and families.

Obesity Prevalence in Local Communities

Orange County has seen an increase in children who are overweight or obese in the last five years. Between 2018 and 2019, the proportion of O.C. students who are overweight or obese increased by 0.3 and 0.6 percentage points respectively (The Orange County Community Indicators Team, 2020). In 2022, approximately 19% of fifth-grade students in Orange County were classified as obese (Orange County Children’s Partnership, 2022). This same report found that one in four (25.7%) 5th grade students who were “economically disadvantaged” were at greater risk for obesity in comparison to one in 10 (10.2%) “economically advantaged” students. Hispanic fifth graders had the highest obesity risk at 27.2% among O.C.’s racial and ethnic groups. Approximately 34.3% of O.C. students in the fifth, seventh, and ninth grades were overweight or obese in 2019, compared to 32.8% in 2014. The school districts of Santa Ana and Anaheim, two of the cities where this DNP project occurred, had the highest rates of obesity, 52% and 50%, respectively. In comparison, Newport Mesa, the school district for Costa Mesa, had an overweight or obesity rate of 30%. The report also found that the students in these grades have declined in their Health Fitness Zone for Aerobic Capacity, a physical fitness test for all students in California, from 70.7% in 2018 to 67.9 % in 2019 (Orange County Children’s Partnership, 2022).

Obesity Prevention in Children

Obesity prevention includes healthier lifestyle changes such as eating lower-calorie foods, like fruits and vegetables, and limiting saturated fats. Reducing screen time, getting adequate quality sleep, and increasing physical activity are also essential (NHLBI, 2022c). Creating and implementing lifestyle changes for a child with obesity can be challenging since it often takes a commitment from the entire family to support new dietary and exercise plans. There are evidence-based guidelines for the prevention and treatment of childhood obesity available to healthcare providers. Strong recommendations for children and adolescents aged 2 to 18 years include family-based multicomponent behavioral interventions that address behavior change, diet, and physical activity (Guideline Development Panel for Treatment of Obesity, American Psychological Association [APA], 2020). These interventions are more successful with a minimum of 26 contact hours with a health care provider, initiated at the earliest age possible. These 26 contact hours may be interventions that address behavior change, diet, and physical activity. Most recently The American Academy of Pediatrics (Hampl et al., 2023) affirmed that intensive health behavior and lifestyle treatment (IHBI) is the foundational approach to reducing excessive weight gain and decreasing body mass in overweight and obese children. This approach also emphasizes family-centered care and coordination by the child's medical home. There is also considerable evidence that physical activity interventions alone can reduce the risk of obesity in children ages 6 to 12 years (Brown et al., 2019).

The Link Between Asthma, Obesity, and Physical Activity

Chen et al. (2017), Shan et al. (2020), Stateski et al. (2002), and Zhang et al. (2020) found that the association between asthma and obesity in children is bidirectional, and both health conditions affect participation in physical activity. In a sample of 8716 children, Stateski

et al. (2022) found that children with asthma were 23% more likely to develop obesity than their non-asthmatic peers. In a systematic review and meta-analysis, Shan et al. (2020) found a significant association between asthma and the risk of childhood obesity. This meta-analysis included two studies on children from Southern California. The first study by Chen et al. (2017) was on a sample of 2,684 children. This study revealed that children with asthma had a 51% increased risk of developing obesity compared to children without asthma. In comparison, in a study of 5,193 children, Zhang et al. (2020), found that children with asthma were 37% more likely to become obese by their next annual visit. Shan et al. (2020) also found a significant association between obesity and an increased risk of asthma in children and adolescents. However, the research studies pooled in the meta-analysis by Shan et al. were reviewed over eight years ago. Therefore, newer research is needed to continue to investigate this bidirectional relationship.

Children with asthma and obesity have increased reported physical activity limitations compared with normal weight children (Wiesenthal et al., 2016). Children with asthma and activity limitations were found to be two times more likely to be overweight or obese (Holderness et al., 2017). In a study of 324 urban children ages 3 to 10 with poorly controlled asthma, those with more severe symptoms reported limitations in gym class (58% vs. 43%) and even in mild activities (28% vs. 14%) compared with their peers with more mild symptoms (Holderness et al., 2017). Additionally, only 39% of the children participated in one or more hours of physical activity per day, and 35% of the children reported no safe place to exercise. These findings add to the evidence that barriers limit physical activity in children with asthma and increase their risk of developing obesity. However, decreased physical activity in children

did not affect lung function and was not associated with an increased risk of developing asthma (Cassim et al., 2019; Leinnar et al., 2016).

Throughout the literature, researchers agreed that the link between obesity and asthma is complex (Fainardi et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2016). Obesity is a comorbidity often found in poorly controlled asthma, indicating an obese-asthma phenotype in children (Fainardi et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2016). Therefore, the increase in obesity prevalence in children is concerning as we observe a parallel increase in obesity-associated asthma. Children with comorbidities of asthma and obesity have decreased physical activity and increased risk of poorer health outcomes. Therefore, healthcare providers must implement interventions to address asthma, obesity, and physical inactivity.

Family-Centered Community-Based Interventions

The literature supports family-centered interventions that address obesity management, including physical activity (Brown et al., 2016; Guideline Development Panel for Treatment of Obesity, APA, 2020; Hampl et al., 2023). In comparison to obesity education in a clinic-only setting, integrating a community setting, such as partnerships with parks and recreation departments, has made significant impacts on increasing physical activity in obese children, especially in low-income minority children ages five to 11 years (Hoffman et al., 2018).

The literature is saturated with recommendations for culturally appropriate community-based and family-centered education that addresses negative perceptions and increases parental knowledge of physical activity in children with asthma (Eisenberg et al., 2020; Islamovic et al., 2019; Jago et al., 2017; Kornblit et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2017). Recommendations to incorporate physical activity counseling into asthma management practice is a newer concept

(Nyenhuis et al., 2022). Nonetheless, the literature shows that adding physical activity education can reduce the risk of obesity in children with asthma.

To promote higher levels of physical activity among the U.S. population, interventions are needed at various levels, including individual, group, and community (King et al., 2019; USDHHS, 2018). The Office of Disease Prevention and Health Promotion (ODPHP, 2023) has created a community-based campaign called *Move Your Way* to encourage more Americans to work toward and meet the *Physical Activity Guidelines for Americans*. The ODPHP promotes the implementation of this campaign at community-based organizations with implementation strategies outlined in the *Community Playbook*, which offers printed and online resources in English and Spanish for both consumers and healthcare providers.

Summary of the Review of Literature

Access to community-based care through the Asthma and Community Outreach Program, combined with the implementation of NAEPP guidelines, has improved asthma control in children, including obese children (Morphew & Galant, 2019). However, implementing physical activity counseling into routine asthma education is still needed. According to the Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA), a high-impact management intervention includes improved asthma education access (Reddel et al., 2021). In addition, effective asthma management requires a partnership between the person with asthma or the caregiver and their healthcare provider (Reddel et al., 2021). These guidelines are based on the most up-to-date evidence in asthma management. This further supports the evidence that a community-based and family-centered intervention to increase physical activity in children can lead to a reduced risk of obesity in these children. This approach is also a step in reducing health disparities in families with children with asthma and obesity.

Methods

The methods section discusses the design, setting, participants, ethical considerations, data collection and management, and evaluation of this DNP project.

Design

This DNP project used a pre-test/post-test survey study design to evaluate the effectiveness of a community-based, family-centered educational program for parents of school-aged children with asthma in the WoW program. The objective of this DNP project was to develop education for these parents and caregivers of school-aged, underserved children with asthma, with the intention of future implementation of these educational programs at WoW. The educational session centered on enhancing knowledge, altering parental perceptions of exercise and asthma, fostering increased physical activity among the children and their families, and facilitating connections to local community physical activity opportunities. The education was offered in English and Spanish.

Setting

This was a multi-site project and took place at three locations in Orange County, California, including: 1) the Boys and Girls Club in Santa Ana, 2) the Boys and Girls Club in Costa Mesa, and 3) the Downtown Anaheim Community Center, all family resource centers in partnership with WoW. These centers were chosen because they were safe and easily accessible to their respective communities. The Boys and Girls Clubs of Santa Ana and Costa Mesa and the Downtown Anaheim Community Center are considered stakeholders for WoW. Having the sessions at these locations provided parents with a secure environment for education, knowledge of a safe location for future family physical activity, and awareness of community resources and support.

Participants

Convenience sampling was utilized to recruit parents of children with asthma, ages 6 to 11 years, who are established WoW patients. A recruitment flyer was posted at the clinical sites (Appendix E). The Principal Investigator (PI) flagged eligible participants on the day of a scheduled routine visit based on the child's age criteria. If the other inclusion criteria were met, the participant was asked if they would like to participate in the project. The following inclusion criteria for the participants were: 1) parent or caregiver of a child aged 6 to 11 years with diagnosed asthma who is an established patient of WoW, 2) parent/caregiver is ≥ 18 years of age, 3) parent/caregiver has access to email, and 4) parent/caregiver is fluent in English and/or Spanish. The exclusion criteria were as follows: 1) parent or caregiver of a child aged ≤ 5 or ≥ 12 years, and 2) lack of English or Spanish literacy.

Recruitment occurred for approximately eight weeks during September and October 2023. Initially, 25 participants were expected to attend each education session, one in English and one in Spanish at each location. The educational session intervention occurred approximately one month after the start of recruitment at each of the three locations. Twenty-two participants were recruited, with the largest group being from the city of Santa Ana.

Ethical Considerations

This DNP project qualified for waiver of informed consent and HIPAA authorization (Appendix F). All participants were at least 18 years old. The principal investigator, co-investigators have completed CITI training and complied with applicable laws and policies to protect personal health information. Written approval (Appendix G) of this DNP project was obtained from the Physician Lead of WoW. This DNP project also received approval from the organization's Nursing Research and Innovation Council (NRIC) prior to applying to the

organization's Institutional Review Board (IRB). After approval from the organization's IRB, an application to the CSULA IRB was submitted and approved. To protect the autonomy of the parent or caregiver, recruitment was voluntary. The information flyers and questionnaires were available in English and Spanish. The approved IRB documents were translated by an organization-approved translator that works with the WoW program.

Risks and Benefits

There was minimal risk to subjects participating in this evidence-based practice project. The main risk is a breach of confidentiality which was mitigated through data collection and storage through an encrypted Research Electronic Data Capture [REDCap] database. To ensure privacy, confidentiality, and protection of information, data was stored within encrypted, password-protected files and managed through REDCap. Only project investigators and permitted project personnel had access to the data during and after the project. Additionally, only de-identified aggregate data will be shared.

Potential benefits to participating in the education program included an increased understanding of the importance of physical activity for children with asthma and how to manage their asthma. In addition, participants may have been connected to community resources that aided in supporting family engagement in physical activity. The knowledge gained from this education program project may be used to provide evidence-based physical activity opportunities for patients with asthma and their families in Orange County.

Data Collection and Management

The data collection timeline for the variables and measures were collected in three parts: 1) pre-education, 2) post-education, and 3) one month-post-education (Appendix H).

Pre-education

The first part occurred at the Community Family Resource Center prior to the start of the education session. Eligible participants were checked into the education session with the WoW supervisor, using the Excel tracking tool. The tracking tool helped to identify which participants needed to be sent a follow-up survey one month after the educational event. Prior to the education session, participants completed a baseline REDCap survey from a Quick Response (QR) code link (Appendix I). The survey was offered in English or Spanish. The participants chose to take the survey in their preferred language. Participants were prompted to create a unique identifier in REDCap (the last four digits of their cell phone number followed by two digits representing their birth month). This served as their project ID number. The survey collected de-identified demographic characteristics (Appendix J); as well as parents' knowledge, perceptions, and beliefs; their child's symptoms with exercise; current physical activities; and community needs and barriers. The QR code was accessible via a smartphone. An institutional approved tablet was also available for use if needed.

Post-education

The second part occurred after the educational session at the community resource center. The participants received the QR code with the link for the REDCap survey that repeated all the questions asked in the baseline survey except for the demographics portion. This second survey assessed if knowledge and perceptions changed post-education sessions. After the educational sessions, participants received a physical activity goal worksheet and were asked to create a specific physical activity goal for their family (Appendix K).

One Month Post-Education

The third REDCap survey was sent out to participants one month after the educational event via an email link. The questions in the third survey contained the same questions in the post-intervention survey. It aimed to determine changes in physical activity and the family's ongoing connection to physical activity opportunities. Additionally, the one-month survey evaluated whether participants and their family members achieved any of the goals from their physical activity worksheet (Appendix K).

Measurement Tools

The surveys consisted of single selection text and five-point Likert scale items, adapted from the literature with permission from the original authors (Kornbilt et al. 2018; Lang et al. 2004; Nathan et al., 2004). Data was collected in four categories: 1) demographic information, 2) asthma and physical activity history, 3) parental knowledge, perceptions, and beliefs, and 4) community assessment of needs and barriers.

Demographic Characteristics. The participants filled out a survey with de-identified, single-select, multi-select, or free-text questions that collected the demographic variables, including relationship to the child (patient), age of the child (patient), age of parent/caregiver, race/ethnicity of the parent/caregiver, gender of the parent/caregiver, number of family members (adults and children) living in the household, and zip code.

Asthma Symptoms and Physical Activity Characteristics. Children's asthma symptoms and physical activity were assessed with five-point Likert-type scales. Participants were asked to indicate how often each statement occurred ranging from "never" to "always." Questions concerning asthma and physical activity were adapted from the validated Asthma Control Test (ACT), with authorization obtained from Nathan et al. (2004), for the purpose of

evaluating asthma management. Additionally, elements were drawn from a questionnaire employed by Lang et al. (2004) in their investigation involving children diagnosed with asthma. To measure if children are meeting the physical activity guidelines, the author created a question in consideration of the physical activity guidelines for children (USDHHS, 2018) and used a question, with permission by Greenwood et al. (2010), from the Physical Activity Vital Sign (PAVS) questionnaire to assess physical activity. The author created two questions to assess parent/caregiver perception of asthma severity by recalling information on visits to the ED and corticosteroid medication with a yes or no response.

Knowledge, Perceptions, and Beliefs. The participants were asked to indicate how much they agreed with each statement with responses ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree” using a Likert-type scale adapted with permission from a study by Lang et al. (2004) that investigated physical activity in urban school-aged children. The APA (n.d.) defines knowledge as the range of one’s understanding, familiarity, and awareness of the information resulting from experience. In comparison, perceptions result from being aware of objections, events, or relationships through activities such as recognizing, observing, or describing, which leads to meaningful knowledge (APA, n.d.). Fear can be a short-term but intense emotion due to an immediate reaction to something concerning a threat or cause for alarm (APA, n.d.). Belief is defined as accepting the truth, reality, or validity of something (APA, n.d.).

Community Assessment Needs and Barriers. Data was collected on the children’s and families’ physical activity status and limitations or barriers (e.g., time, neighborhood) to physical activity. The first three questions were adapted from a parent evaluation form developed by the NHLBI (n.d.) to evaluate a physical activity and nutrition program for children and parents called “We Can!” and the Lang et al. (2004) study. The last question was adapted with

permission from Kornbilt's (2018) study that measured parental perspectives of barriers to physical activity in urban school-aged children with asthma. For this DNP project, a five-point Likert scale was used to measure community needs and barriers by asking how likely respondents were to agree with each statement.

Goal Setting. At the end of the educational session, parents and caregivers received a physical activity goal worksheet. An example of how to fill it out was given, and examples of physical activities were provided. Parents were instructed to choose one physical activity as a goal for the child and one physical activity as a goal for the entire family to be done in four weeks. Goal setting is a process where the parent/caregiver can establish a specific, time-based behavior target that is measurable, achievable, and realistic (APA, n.d.). They are clear objectives with measurable criteria, feasible to accomplish, relevant to the individual's life, and have a defined timeline. According to the APA, goal setting is only effective if the individual is aware of what is to be accomplished and believes it is attainable. The SMART acronym (e.g., Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, Timebound) is a recognized approach for establishing physical activity objectives (Swann et al., 2023) and has been used in family-centered lifestyle interventions (Deslippe et al., 2023). For this intervention, the parents and caregivers were provided with a brief outline on how to set a SMART goal.

Intervention Plan

The author of this DNP project developed an educational curriculum (Appendix N) and a PowerPoint presentation that was delivered in English and Spanish sessions in a classroom space at the community center. The author considered health literacy and made information easy to find, understandable, and accessible to allow the parent or caregiver to grasp the content better.

The author used clear and simple guides with evidence-based and culturally appropriate tips on how to design health education materials and presentations.

The educational content on asthma came from the Wee Breathers Program (Asthma and Allergy Foundation of America [AAFA], (2013). This program was designed to help health professionals educate parents of young children with asthma and the lessons are provided at the 6th grade reading level (Appendix O). This educational content aligns with the evidence-based guidelines from the NAEPP (2007).

The physical activity and exercise educational content was taken from *Move Your Way*, an evidence- and community-based campaign created by the ODPHP (2023) and promoted by the CDC to implement the U.S. *Physical Activity Guidelines* (USDHHS, 2018). A fact sheet for parents (Appendices P and Q) and one for children (Appendices R and S) were utilized in the educational presentation and were made available during these educational sessions. After the educational session was complete, the WoW Supervisor and the Community Resource Center Program Director from each site provided information about physical activity opportunities in the center and surrounding community.

Learning Objectives

Upon completing this educational session, the participants should be able to meet the following learning objectives: 1) describe the benefits of physical activity for children with asthma, 2) identify appropriate physical activities, and 3) develop goals to include physical activity in their families' daily lives.

Evaluation Plan

The project aimed to assess the efficacy of community-based, family-centered education for parents of school-aged children with asthma by focusing on improving parental knowledge

and understanding of the importance of physical activity. It also aimed to help the family develop goals to include physical activity as a part of their daily lives. The evaluation plan included both pre- and post-education surveys. Before the educational session, baseline surveys gauged participants' knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs concerning physical activity for children with asthma. Following the completion of the educational session, surveys were administered to assess changes in the participants' comprehension of the benefits of physical activity in their children with asthma. The one-month survey evaluated whether the participants met their physical activity goals for integrating physical activity into their families' daily lives. This last survey aimed to capture the impact of education in promoting physical activity for children with asthma and assess if there were any changes to community needs or barriers.

Data Analysis

The distribution of survey responses was reported in a descriptive table. Continuous variables were presented as mean, median, and standard deviation, while categorical variables were reported using frequencies and proportions. A paired Wilcoxon rank-sum test was employed to assess the differences in ordinal variables in pre- and post-intervention groups.

Results

Demographic Characteristics

Although 22 parents or caregivers were recruited, only nine parents participated in the educational sessions. Four participants attended an educational session at the Downtown Anaheim Family Resource Center, three at the Santa Ana Boys and Girls Club, and two at the Costa Mesa Boys and Girls Club. Language preferences were identified during the recruitment process, with one participant choosing the English session and eight choosing the Spanish session. Out of the four sessions only one session was in English, while the remaining three were in Spanish.

One participant chose the “post-education” survey instead of “pre-intervention” survey resulting in missed sociodemographic data. As seen in Table 1 (Appendix T), the pre-education survey collected information on age, ethnicity, race, gender, age of the child with asthma, and family household. The highest percentage of participants fell in the age range from 35 to 44 years (62.5%). All eight participants self-identified their ethnicity as Hispanic/Latino. One participant racially identified as White, while the remaining seven chose not to disclose their race. In terms of gender, one participant identified as he, while seven participants identified as she. One participant identified as a father, and the rest identified as mothers. The participants’ children were between the ages of six and ten years old and lived in households with four to six family members. All participants were parents of children with asthma receiving care with WoW and had Medi-Cal insurance.

Asthma Symptoms and Physical Activity Characteristics

One participant chose the “post-education” survey instead of the “pre-education” survey resulting in missing information on asthma and physical activity characteristics baseline. Table 2

(Appendix U) shows baseline survey data collected from parents of children with asthma to explore various factors related to physical exercise and asthma management, including the intensity and duration of exercise, asthma symptoms during physical activity, the use of albuterol inhalers post-exercise, ED visits due to asthma symptoms, and the utilization of oral corticosteroids for asthma control. The participants rated their children's asthma symptoms and physical activity using a five-point Likert-type scale with responses ranging from "never," to "always."

The results revealed that, 62.5% of the participants reported that their children "often" participated in physical activity for 60 minutes or more per day and 62.5% of the participants reported that their children "sometimes" engaged in vigorous physical activity. However, 37.5% of the participants reported that their child was in the ED for asthma symptoms in the last 12 months. Additionally, oral corticosteroid usage for asthma symptom control was prevalent among the children of the participants, with 62.5% of the participants reporting that their child used it in the last 12 months. In addition, 50% of the parents reported that their children "sometimes" have trouble with asthma during physical activity, while 25% reported that their children "often" have trouble with exercise. Similarly, 37.5% of the parents reported that their children "sometimes" used albuterol (SABA) after exercise whereas 25% reported that they "often" did.

Knowledge, Perceptions, and Beliefs

Nine participants answered the pre-education component of this survey, but only eight completed the post-education survey. The participants were asked to indicate how much they agreed with each statement, with responses ranging from "strongly disagree," to "strongly agree." Table 3 (Appendix V) shows the analysis and stratification by time period (pre- and post-

intervention) of the survey responses. Overall, there were no statistically significant differences observed between the pre- and post-intervention groups across the survey components. However, due to the small sample size, the ability to detect significant effects with less than a 50% difference in distribution between the two samples was limited.

The analysis of this small group of parents found no statistically ($p < 0.05$) significant differences between pre- and post-intervention groups across various Likert survey components. However, participants showed agreement on the “importance of physical activity for all children” with the mean shifting from 4.5 (agree) pre- intervention to 5 (strongly agree) post- intervention. Similarly, participants agreed that “children with asthma should engage in physical activity” with the mean of 4 (agree) pre intervention to a 5 (strongly agree) post-intervention.

As seen in Table 4, (Appendix W) there was a notable shift observed in perceptions related to “physical activity may make a child’s asthma better.” Three out of eight participants (37.5%) positively shifted from “undecided” pre-intervention to “agree” or “strongly agree” post-intervention. Similarly, as seen in Table 5, (Appendix X) five out of nine participants (56%) initially agreed with the statement “I am afraid that my child will get sick if he or she does physical activity, exercise, or sports.” However, post-intervention there were also notable positive shifts observed in perceptions. Two out of eight participants shifted from “undecided” to “disagree” and “strongly disagree.” while another two participants shifted from “disagree” to “strongly disagree.” Additionally, two of the eight participants changed their position from “agree” to “disagree.” Therefore, post-intervention 50% of the participants positively shifted their beliefs.

Community Assessment Needs and Barriers

Nine participants answered the pre-education survey of this portion but only eight completed the post-education survey. A five-point Likert-scale rated community needs and barriers by asking how likely participants were to agree with each statement, with responses ranging from "very unlikely" to "very likely." Table 3 (Appendix V) shows the analysis and stratification by time period (pre- and post-intervention) of the survey responses. Overall, there were no statistically significant differences observed between the pre- and post-intervention groups across the survey components. The most notable change in perception or belief was observed regarding the statement, "there is not enough time in the day for physical activity." Responses shifted from a median of 4 (agree) before the intervention to 2 (disagree) after the intervention. As seen in Table 6 (Appendix W) a closer look at each participant's response showed that five out of nine (56%) participants initially agreed that there is not enough time in the day for physical activity. Post-intervention, three out of eight participants (37.5%) positively shifted from agree to disagree.

One Month Post Survey

There was only one participant who completed the one-month post survey. The one-month post survey asked participants to indicate whether they agree or disagree with the statement "There is not enough time in the day to be physically active." The parent/caregiver agreed with this statement. Additionally, the participants were asked to respond with either "Yes" or "No" to the question, "Was the physical activity goal for your child, created during the education session, achieved within the last month?" If they selected "No," they were further prompted to specify some contributing barriers to not achieving the physical activity goal for their child, choosing from options such as "not enough time," "no safe or convenient place," "my

child was sick,” or “other.” This participant responded with a “no” and chose the option “not enough time.”

Discussion

Children with asthma face an increased risk of obesity, leading to poor asthma control and worse health outcomes compared to their non-obese peers (CDC, 2023; Chen et al., 2017; Holderness et al., 2017; Stratakis et al., 2022; Zang et al., 2018). An intervention that provides education on the role of physical activity in asthma management can mitigate obesity risk in these children, thus reducing overall asthma morbidity (Reddel et al., 2021). WoW addresses the healthcare needs of underserved children with asthma and their families and has observed a concerning increase in obesity rates among these children. At the time of this DNP Project, WoW did not have a standardized curriculum specifically tailored to address obesity prevention in this population.

This evidence-based DNP project aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of a community-based, family-centered education program for parents of school-aged children with asthma, intending to increase their understanding of the importance of physical activity in their asthma management. This section provides an analysis of the findings from the evidence-based practice project. It also discusses the impact of these findings on nursing and clinical practice, explores potential avenues for future research projects, addresses considerations for sustainability, and presents limitations of this project.

Demographic Characteristics

The pre-education survey results, which included demographic data such as parent age, ethnicity, race, and gender, uncovered interesting insights into the characteristics of the participants. The sample's demographic homogeneity, characterized by participants of similar income, age, race, gender, offers focused insights into factors, behaviors, and experiences related to physical activity in children with asthma within this group of Hispanic/Latino parents limited

generalizability (Grove & Gray, 2019). Notably, a considerable number of parents chose not to disclose their race, a trend commonly observed in this population and in other studies, often resulting in an "unknown" race category (Magaña López et al., 2017).

In this DNP project, with only one father participating compared to eight mothers, there is a risk that fathers' perceptions of physical activity may be underrepresented. The lack of fathers, especially from disadvantaged backgrounds, in pediatric research limits understanding of their impact on children's health and the effectiveness of family interventions (Davison et al., 2017). Davison et al., also found that fathers are more likely to participate when the time commitment is minimal, and the benefits for fathers and families are clear while also emphasized the vital role of community partners in connecting with fathers.

Asthma Symptoms and Physical Activity Characteristics

The results of this DNP project suggest that a significant portion of children with asthma in the survey population required oral steroids to manage their asthma symptoms, as indicated by the high prevalence of oral corticosteroid usage (62.5%). In addition, 37.5% of the participants reported that their child had been in the ED for asthma symptoms in the last 12 months. Oral systemic corticosteroids are used to manage acute asthma exacerbations and severe symptoms (Tran et al., 2021). Therefore, these findings may imply that a considerable number of these children have asthma that is not well-controlled with standard maintenance medications alone, necessitating the use of oral corticosteroids for symptom management.

Additionally, the fact that 37.5% of all patients surveyed reported “sometimes “using albuterol after exercise indicates that EIB symptoms are relatively common among these children. Furthermore, the high incidence of trouble with asthma during exercise reported by half of the respondents (50%) highlights a significant issue with asthma control during physical

activity (Reddel et al., 2021). The results emphasize the necessity for tailored management strategies, like adjusting treatment regimens or implementing preventive measures before physical activity, to address EIA symptoms. Overall, it stresses the importance of personalized strategies for managing asthma and implementing interventions to improve asthma control specifically during physical activity. Enhancing awareness of EIB symptoms and risk factors, along with improving diagnosis accuracy and educating patients on SABA usage for symptom prevention, are crucial for optimizing symptom control (Aggarwal et al., 2017).

Knowledge, Perceptions, and Beliefs

Overall, there were no statistically significant differences between the pre- and post-intervention groups across the survey components. However, participants showed agreement on the “importance of physical activity for all children” with the mean shifting from 4.5 (agree) pre-intervention to 5 (strongly agree) post-intervention. Similarly, participants agreed that “children with asthma should engage in physical activity” with the mean of 4 (agree) pre intervention to a 5 (strongly agree) post-intervention.

In comparison, there was a general disagreement regarding concerns about physical activity exacerbating asthma symptoms or being unsafe. A closer look at each participants response showed a change in perceptions regarding the statement "physical activity may improve a child's asthma" and "I am afraid that my child will get sick if he or she does physical activity, exercise, or sports." These findings indicate that the intervention positively influenced these participants' perceptions of the relationship between physical activity and childhood asthma management. The shift from uncertainty to agreement suggests an increased acceptance and understanding of the benefits of physical activity in managing asthma in children.

The findings of this DNP project align with existing literature regarding the correlation between parental perceptions and fear of asthma symptoms related to physical activity (Eisenberg et al., 2020; Islamovic et al., 2019; Koinis-Mitchell et al., 2021; Kornblit et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2017). Although, the project did not determine the extent of this influence on children's physical activity levels, it highlights that parents have concerns about their children developing asthma symptoms during physical activities. Therefore, the findings suggest that educating these parents about the importance of physical activity for their children with asthma could potentially alter their perceptions and beliefs, thereby increasing physical activity in their child's life.

Community Assessment Needs and Barriers

A notable change was observed in perceptions related to the availability of time for physical activity, with a shift from agreement to disagreement post-intervention. These results suggest a positive shift in attitude and belief regarding the importance of allocating time for physical activity among parents of children with asthma. Despite a slight shift mean of 4 (agree) pre intervention to a median of 2 (disagree) post-intervention regarding perceived time constraints for physical activity, this difference was also not statistically significant. Despite this observed shift, the lack of statistical significance indicates the need for further research with larger sample sizes to validate these findings and provide deeper insights into the reasons behind the lack of availability of time for physical activity and/or the lack of safe community spaces available for exercise.

Goal Setting

Only one out of nine participants completed the one-month post-follow-up survey. What stood out was that the participant acknowledged the difficulty of dedicating enough time in the

day for physical activity for their child and therefore they were unable to ensure that their child achieved their physical activity goal in the month after the intervention was completed.

Implications for Nursing

The doctorally prepared Nurse Practitioner should be uniquely skilled in translating research and incorporating evidence-based practice (EBP) to tailor interventions which address the unique healthcare challenges of underserved populations while also ensuring cultural sensitivity. Therefore, doctorally prepared Pediatric Nurse Practitioners can have a pivotal role in managing population health by addressing the complex health issues of obesity in children with asthma and developing collaborative, family-centered, and community-focused interventions (Buckley & Bennett-Murray., 2018; Schneider & Panton, 2024). This approach underscores the holistic nature of nursing care and the importance of engaging families and communities in interventions.

Implications for Clinical Practice

It is recommended that WoW incorporate culturally appropriate community-based and family-centered education to enhance parental knowledge of physical activity in children with asthma. The creation of an educational program regarding the importance of physical activity asthma has been well documented (Eisenberg et al., 2020; Islamovic et al., 2019; Jago et al., 2017; Kornblit et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2017). In addition, integrating physical activity counseling into asthma management practices has shown promise in reducing obesity risk among children with asthma (Nyenhuis et al., 2022). Therefore, this DNP project can be a model for nursing led education for the families of WoW. In addition, other school districts with high overweight or obesity rates in O.C., such as Garden Grove (41%), Orange (38%), and Fullerton (36%) should be included (The Orange County Community Indicators Team (2020). The

potential for providing further support for these communities is promising, as WoW has community partnerships located in these at these cities as well.

Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) are traumatic events in childhood that lead to toxic stress and are the primary drivers of many significant health and social issues in California (DHCS, 2024 c). Asthma is among ACE-Associated Health Conditions in school aged children DHCS (2024a). In addition, ACEs is also associated with an increased risk of childhood obesity and research has shown that raising awareness of ACEs would benefit childhood obesity prevention (Hampl et al., 2023; Schroeder et al., 2021).

The ACEs Aware initiative is a nationwide effort to screen patients for ACES to help improve the lives of children, families, and communities (DHCS, 2024 c). Part of this nationwide effort is for clinicians to educate their patients on the seven evidence-based stress busters (DHCS, 2024b). The stress busters are clinical strategies that help manage or prevent toxic stress and one effective stress buster is physical activity (DHCS, 2024a). ACES Aware has created multiple resource handouts to educate families and communities on the seven stress busters. The author of this project recommends integrating the physical activity stressbuster handout into this DNP project educational program. The handout acknowledges how limited time affects families' ability to engage in physical activity and offers practical strategies to overcome this barrier to effectively incorporate physical activity into daily routines (Appendix Z). This handout can also be given out during a clinic visit when discussing the importance of physical activity in asthma management.

Implications for Research

A research study could examine how this educational intervention reduces the risk of obesity in children with asthma by measuring BMI and other health outcomes. Other long-term

outcomes could include sustained physical activity participation by families and utilization of community resources. This DNP project provides valuable insights into conducting research on underserved Hispanic parents of children with asthma. A particularly noteworthy discovery is that this group did not have high response rates to invitations or questionnaires sent via email. Therefore, any future research proposals must prioritize cultural sensitivity to engage with and gather data from this population effectively with and gather data from this population.

Implications for Sustainability

The findings of this evidence-based project highlight the significance of family and community partnerships in enhancing asthma education and overcoming obstacles to physical activity among the urban communities served by WoW. Community partnerships with other underserved communities in O.C. can help remove barriers to physical activity in the urban communities that WoW serves by linking families with community resource centers and organizations that offer physical activity opportunities for the entire family. The support of WoW leadership in leveraging these community partners will be essential for sustaining a tailored educational program. It would also be important for the community partners to evaluate the impact of the community resources and services (such as physical activity opportunities) provided and utilized by the families.

Limitations

The primary limitations of this DNP project were the limited sample size and the restricted time period for project completion. The initial session encountered challenges as participants recruited in person exhibited low responsiveness to email invitations and failing to RSVP for the session. This led to uncertainty regarding the actual number of participants and their attendance. Confirmation via phone call was later used as a secondary measure and

provided more responses in this sample population. Sessions were scheduled on weekdays during school hours, potentially limiting the availability of parents to attend due to work commitments or childcare responsibilities, especially considering that 62.5% of the participants having a family household of six members.

Another major limitation was that one of the participants chose the post-education survey instead of the pre-test survey prior to the start of the education. This led to missing demographic data and information on the child's asthma symptoms and physical activity baseline. At the end of the education one participant left before completing the post-education survey. The parent was asked to complete at home, but it was not done. Therefore, this limited the author of this project to analyze if there were any changes of perceptions post-intervention for this particular participant.

Another limitation was that only one participant completed the one-month post-follow-up survey. As a result, there was insufficient information to evaluate whether parents achieved the goals they had set during the educational sessions or to identify any changes in their community needs or barriers. Additionally, time constraints during the educational sessions may have impacted the effectiveness of goal setting. Although instructions covered the essential components of SMART goal setting, limited time might have hindered the participants' understanding of and commitment of their goals.

To address these limitations, future educational sessions should adopt a multifaceted approach. In addition, cultural sensitivity should be emphasized, and clear communication in recruitment, engagement, and retention within the Hispanic/Latino community should be implemented. Prioritizing the removal of barriers such as childcare, transportation, and frequent

telephone contact to remind families of the intervention date is essential when engaging this patient population (Aguirre et al., 2018; Cui et al., 2019; DeFrank et al., 2019).

Therefore, to improve response rates and engagement, broadening communication strategies beyond emails includes incorporating various channels like social media, phone calls, or community flyers (DeFrank et al., 2019). Offering sessions during evenings and weekends may accommodate various schedules, making participation more accessible (Aguirre et al., 2018; Cui et al., 2019). To mitigate barriers related to childcare responsibilities, providing childcare services, or organizing activities for the participants' children during sessions may be crucial (Aguirre et al., 2018; Cui et al., 2019; DeFrank et al., 2019). Additionally, incorporating online participation options facilitates access for those facing transportation challenges (Aguirre et al., 2018; Cui et al., 2019; DeFrank et al., 2019). All members of the WoW team could benefit from education and training on how to achieve this objective. By implementing these recommendations, future educational sessions can become more inclusive, accessible, and effective in reaching a wider audience.

Conclusion

This DNP project offers insights into the challenges faced by a specific group of Hispanic/Latino parents of the patients of the WOW program. This project emphasizes the importance of parental awareness in prioritizing physical activity for their children. Parental involvement is crucial in educational interventions aimed at promoting physical activity among Hispanic children with asthma, who face a higher risk of obesity. The findings in this project align with existing literature regarding the connection between parental perceptions and the fear of asthma symptoms (Eisenberg et al., 2020; Islamovic et al., 2019; Koinis-Mitchell et al., 2021; Kornblit et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2017). However, the project falls short of determining the

precise impact of these factors on children's physical activity levels. Nonetheless, it sheds light on the concerns parents have about their children encountering asthma symptoms during physical activities. Most importantly, the project suggests that educating parents about the significance of physical activity for their children could potentially shift their perceptions, potentially leading to positive changes in behavior and attitudes toward physical activity management in children with asthma. It is crucial to mitigate barriers of time constraints to improve parental involvement in promoting physical activity among Hispanic children with asthma, which can be done by continuing to provide education and support.

References

- Abdelbasset, W. K., Alsubaie, S. F., Tantawy, S. A., Abo Elyazed, T. I., & Kamel, D. M. (2018). Evaluating pulmonary function, aerobic capacity, and pediatric quality of life following a 10-week aerobic exercise training in school-aged asthmatics: A randomized controlled trial. *Patient Preference and Adherence*, *12*, 1015–1023.
<https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S159622>
- Aggarwal, B., Mulgirigama, A., & Berend, N. (2018). Exercise-induced bronchoconstriction: prevalence, pathophysiology, patient impact, diagnosis, and management. *NPJ Primary Care Respiratory Medicine*, *28*(1), 31–38. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41533-018-0098-2>
- Aguirre, T. M., Koehler, A. E., Joshi, A., & Wilhelm, S. L. (2018). Recruitment and retention challenges and successes. *Ethnicity & Health*, *23*(1), 111–119.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13557858.2016.1246427>
- Asthma and Allergy Foundation of America. (2013). *Instructor's guide: Wee Breathers asthma education for families and young children*. <https://www.aafa.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/wee-breathers-full-program-english.pdf>
- American College of Allergy, Asthma, and Immunology. (2021). *Exercise-induced bronchoconstriction (EIB)*. Asthma. <https://acaai.org/asthma/types-of-asthma/exerciseinduced-bronchoconstriction-eib/>
- American College of Sports Medicine. (2021a). *Being active with your young child*. Exercise is Medicine. <https://www.exerciseismedicine.org/eim-in-action/health-care/resources/rx-for-health-series/>

- American College of Sports Medicine. (2021b). *Being active when you have asthma*. Exercise is Medicine. <https://www.exerciseismedicine.org/eim-in-action/health-care/resources/rx-for-health-series/>
- American Psychological Association. (n.d). *APA dictionary of psychology*. <https://dictionary.apa.org/>
- Banasiak, N. C. (2018). Implementation of the asthma control test in primary care to improve patient outcomes. *Journal of Pediatric Health Care*, 32(6), 591–599. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedhc.2018.05.004>
- Bhagat, D., Fagnano, M., Halterman, J. S., & Reznik, M. (2019). Asthma symptoms, interactive physical play and behavioral and academic outcomes in urban children with persistent asthma. *Journal of Asthma*, 56(7), 711-718. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02770903.2018.1488978>
- Brown, H. E., Atkin, A. J., Panter, J., Wong, G., Chinapaw, M. J. M., & van Sluijs, E. M. F. (2016). Family-based interventions to increase physical activity in children: A systematic review, meta-analysis, and realist synthesis. *Obesity Reviews*, 17(4), 345–360. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.12362>
- Brown, T., Moore, T. H., Hooper, L., Gao, Y., Zayegh, A., Ijaz, S., Elwenspoek, M., Foxen, S. C., Magee, L., O'Malley, C., Waters, E., & Summerbell, C. D. (2019). Interventions for preventing obesity in children. *The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 7(7). <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD001871.pub4>
- Buckley, J., & Bennett-Murray, J. (2018). The role of the nurse practitioner and childhood obesity. *Cultura Del Cuidado*, 15, 27-33. <https://doi.org/10.18041/1794-5232/cultura.2018v15n2.5110>

California Department of Education. (2023). *District of choice supplemental glossary and instructions*. California Department of Education.

www.cde.ca.gov/ds/dc/cb/gidocs.asp?tabsection=1

California Department of Public Health. (2022a). *Asthma inequities in California children*.

https://www.cdph.ca.gov/Programs/CCDPHP/DEODC/EHIB/CPE/CDPH%20Document%20Library/CA_Asthma_Inequities_Children_2021-Infographic.pdf

California Department of Public Health. (2022b). *Asthma prevalence within a county*. California Asthma Dashboard.

<https://www.cdph.ca.gov/Programs/CCDPHP/DEODC/EHIB/CPE/Pages/CaliforniaBreathingCountyAsthmaProfiles.aspx>

Cassim, R., Dharmage, S. C., Koplin, J. J., Milanzi, E., Paro, F. M., & Russell, M. A. (2019).

Does physical activity strengthen lungs and protect against asthma in childhood? A systematic review. *Pediatric Allergy and Immunology*, 30(7), 739–751.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/pai.13105>

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2022a). *About child & teen BMI*. Division of Nutrition, Physical Activity, and Obesity.

https://www.cdc.gov/healthyweight/assessing/bmi/childrens_bmi/about_childrens_bmi.html

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2022b). Social determinants of health at CDC.

<https://www.cdc.gov/socialdeterminants/about.html>

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2023). *Most recent national asthma data*.

https://www.cdc.gov/asthma/most_recent_national_asthma_data.htm

- Chen, T. J., Watson, K. B., Michael, S. L., Minnaert, J. J., Fulton, J. E., & Carlson, S. A. (2021). A new decade of healthy people: Considerations for comparing youth physical activity across 2 surveillance systems. *Journal of Physical Activity & Health, 18*(S1), S94–S101. <https://doi.org/10.1123/JPAH.2021-0015>
- Chen, Z., Salam, M. T., Alderete, T. L., Habre, R., Bastain, T. M., Berhane, K., & Gilliland, F. D. (2017). Effects of childhood asthma on the development of obesity among school-aged children. *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine, 195*(9), 1181–1188. <https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.201608-1691OC>
- Cohen, M., Stephens, C. T. D., Zaheer, A., Instone, S., & Macauley, K. A. (2022). Multilingual postpartum depression screening in pediatric community health clinics. *Journal of Pediatric Health Care, 36*(2), 115–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedhc.2021.02.005>
- Cui, Z., Truesdale, K. P., Robinson, T. N., Pemberton, V., French, S. A., Escarfuller, J., Casey, T. L., Hotop, A. M., Matheson, D., Pratt, C. A., Lotas, L. J., Po'e, E., Andrisin, S., & Ward, D. S. (2019). Recruitment strategies for predominantly low-income, multi-racial/ethnic children and parents to 3-year community-based intervention trials: Childhood obesity prevention and treatment research (COPTR) consortium. *Trials, 20*(1), 296. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-019-3418-0>
- Davison, K. K., Charles, J. N., Khandpur, N., & Nelson, T. J. (2017). Fathers' perceived reasons for their underrepresentation in child health research and strategies to increase their involvement. *Maternal and Child Health Journal, 21*(2), 267–274. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10995-016-2157-z>

- DeFrank, G., Singh, S., Mateo, K. F., Harrison, L., Rosenthal, A., Gorman, A., & Leung, M. M. (2019). Key recruitment and retention strategies for a pilot web-based intervention to decrease obesity risk among minority youth. *Pilot and Feasibility Studies*, *5*(1), 109–109. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40814-019-0492-8>
- Deslippe, A. L., Bains, A., Loiselle, S., Kasvis, P., Mak, I., Weiler, H., & Cohen, T. R. (2023). SMART goals of children of 6–12 years enrolled in a family-centered lifestyle intervention for childhood obesity: Secondary analysis of a randomized controlled trial. *Pediatric Obesity*, *18*(1), e12973-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijpo.12973>
- Eisenberg, S. R., Jelalian, E., Farrow, M., Kopel, S. J., Vehse, N., Mitchell, P., Dunsiger, S., & Koinis-Mitchell, D. (2020). Perceptions of asthma and exercise, and associations with weight status and asthma morbidity in urban children. *Academic Pediatrics*, *20*(1), 55–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acap.2019.07.001>
- Fainardi, V., Passadore, L., Labate, M., Pisi, G., & Esposito, S. (2022). An overview of the obese-asthma phenotype in children. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, *19*(2), 636. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19020636>
- Greenwood, J. L. J., Joy, E. A., & Stanford, J. B. (2010). The physical activity vital sign: A primary care tool to guide counseling for obesity. *Journal of Physical Activity & Health*, *7*(5), 571–576. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.7.5.571>
- Grove, S. K., & Gray, J. R. (2019). *Understanding nursing research. Building an evidence-based Practice*. (7th ed.). Elsevier.

Guideline Development Panel for Treatment of Obesity, American Psychological Association.

(2020). Summary of the clinical practice guideline for multicomponent behavioral treatment of obesity and overweight in children and adolescents. *The American Psychologist*, 75(2), 178–188. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000530>

Hale, R., & Wendler, M. C. (2023). Evidence-based practice: Implementing trauma-informed. Care of children and adolescents in the inpatient psychiatric setting. *Journal of the American Psychiatric Nurses Association*, 29(2), 161–170.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1078390320980045>

Hampl, S. E., Hassink, S. G., Skinner, A. C., Armstrong, S. C., Barlow, S. E., Bolling, C. F., Avila Edwards, K. C., Eneli, I., Hamre, R., Joseph, M. M., Lunsford, D., Mendonca, E., Michalsky, M. P., Mirza, N., Ochoa, E. R., Sharifi, M., Staiano, A. E., Weedn, A. E., Flinn, S. K., Lindros, J., Okechukwu, K. (2023). Clinical practice guideline for the evaluation and treatment of children and adolescents with obesity. *Pediatrics*, 151(2),

<https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2022-060640>

Hoffman, J., Frerichs, L., Story, M., Jones, J., Gaskin, K., Apple, A., Skinner, A., & Armstrong, S. (2018). An integrated clinic-community partnership for child obesity treatment: A randomized pilot trial. *Pediatrics* 141(1) <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2017-1444>

Holderness, H., Chin, N., Ossip, D. J., Fagnano, M., Reznik, M., & Halterman, J. S. (2017).

Physical activity, restrictions in activity, and body mass index among urban children with persistent asthma. *Annals of Allergy, Asthma & Immunology*, 118(4), 433–438.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anai.2017.01.014>

- Islamovic, F., Silver, E. J., & Reznik, M. (2019). Do urban minority parents and children agree on asthma symptoms with exercise, worries, and confidence in disease management? *Academic Pediatrics, 19*(6), 624–630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acap.2019.05.007>
- Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing, 14*(3), 175–182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12223>
- Jago, R., Searle, A., Henderson, A. J., & Turner, K. M. (2017). Designing a physical activity intervention for children with asthma: a qualitative study of the views of healthcare professionals, parents, and children with asthma. *BMJ Open, 7*(3). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-014020>
- King, A. C., Whitt-Glover, M. C., Marquez, D. X., Buman, M. P., Napolitano, M. A., Jakicic, J., Fulton, J. E., & Tennant, B. L. (2019). Physical activity promotion: Highlights from the 2018 physical activity guidelines advisory committee systematic review. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise, 51*(6), 1340–1353. <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000001945>
- Koinis-Mitchell, D., Kopel, S. J., Dunsiger, S., McQuaid, E. L., Miranda, L. G., Mitchell, P., Vehse, N., & Jelalian, E. (2021). Asthma and physical activity in urban children. *Journal of Pediatric Psychology, 46*(8), 970–979. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpepsy/jsab023>
- Kornblit, A., Cain, A., Bauman, L. J., Brown, N. M., & Reznik, M. (2018). Parental perspectives of barriers to physical activity in urban school children with asthma. *Academic Pediatrics, 18*(3), 310–316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acap.2017.12.011>

- Lang, D. M., Butz, A. M., Duggan, A. K., & Serwint, J. R. (2004). Physical activity in urban school-aged children with asthma. *Pediatrics*, *113*(4), e341–e346.
<https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.113.4.e341>
- Lang, J. E. (2019). The impact of exercise on asthma. *Current Opinion in Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, *19*(2), 118–125. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACI.0000000000000510>
- Leinaar, E., Alamian, A., & Wang, L. (2016). A systematic review of the relationship between asthma, overweight, and the effects of physical activity in youth. *Annals of Epidemiology*, *26*(7), 504–510 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annepidem.2016.06.002>
- Lu, K. D., Manoukian, K., Radom-Aizik, S., Cooper, D. M., & Galant, S. P. (2016). Obesity, asthma, and exercise in child and adolescent health. *Pediatric Exercise Science*, *28*(2), 264–274. <https://doi.org/10.1123/pes.2015-0122>
- Manion, A. B., & Velsor-Friedrich, B. (2017). Quality of life and health outcomes in overweight and non-overweight children with asthma. *Journal of Pediatric Health Care: Official Publication of National Association of Pediatric Nurse Associates & Practitioners*, *31*(1), 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pedhc.2016.01.005>
- Morphew, T., & Galant, S. P. (2019). Can asthma be well controlled with NAEPP guideline care in morbidly obese children? The Breathmobile. *Annals of Allergy, Asthma, & Immunology*, *122*(2), 167–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anai.2018.10.019>
- Nathan, R. A., Sorkness, C. A., Kosinski, M., Schatz, M., Li, J. T., Marcus, P., Murray, J. J., & Pendergraft, T. B. (2004). Development of the asthma control test: A survey for assessing asthma control. *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, *113*(1), 59–65.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaci.2003.09.008>

- National Asthma Education and Prevention Program (2007). Expert panel report 3 (EPR-3): Guidelines for the diagnosis and management of asthma-summary report 2007. *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, 120(5 Suppl), S94–S138.
<https://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/health-topics/guidelines-for-diagnosis-management-of-asthma>
- National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute. (n.d). *We can! Parent curriculum evaluation*.
<https://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/health/educational/wecan/downloads/parent-questionnaire.pdf>.
- National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute. (2022a). *Asthma: Causes and triggers*.
<https://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/health/asthma/causes>
- National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute. (2022b). *Asthma: Symptoms*.
<https://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/health/asthma/symptoms>
- National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute. (2022c). *Overweight and obesity: Childhood obesity*
<https://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/health/overweight-and-obesity>
- National Research Corporation [NRC] (2022). Wellness on wheels: An NRC health community insight study.
- Nurmagambetov, T., Kuwahara, R., & Garbe, P. (2018). The economic burden of asthma in the United States, 2008-2013. *Annals of the American Thoracic Society*, 15(3), 348–356.
<https://doi.org/10.1513/AnnalsATS.201703-259OC>
- Nyenhuis, S. M., Kahwash, B., Cooke, A., Gregory, K. L., Greiwe, J., & Nanda, A. (2022). Recommendations for physical activity in asthma: A work group report of the AAAAI sports, exercise, and fitness committee. *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology in Practice*, 10(2), 433–443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaip.2021.10.056>

Orange County Children’s Partnership (2022). *The 28th annual report on the conditions of children in Orange County*. County of Orange, California.

<https://www.ssa.ocgov.com/about-us/news-publications/COCR>.

Orange County Community Indicators Team (2020). *O.C. community indicators 2020-2021*.

<https://www.families-forward.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/2020-Community-Indicators-Report-reduced-size.pdf>

Pate, C. A., Zahran, H. S., Qin, X., Johnson, C., Hummelman, E., & Malilay, J. (2021). Asthma surveillance- United States, 2006-2018. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report. Surveillance summaries (Washington, DC: 2002)*, 70(5), 1–32.

<https://doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.ss7005a1>

Reddel, H. K., Bacharier, L. B., Bateman, E. D., Brightling, C. E., Brusselle, G. G., Buhl, R., Cruz, A. A., Duijts, L., Drazen, J. M., FitzGerald, J. M., Fleming, L. J., Inoue, H., Ko, F. W., Krishnan, J. A., Levy, M. L., Lin, J., Mortimer, K., Pitrez, P. M., Sheikh, A., Yorgancioglu, A. A., Boulet, L. P. (2021). Global initiative for asthma strategy 2021: Executive summary and rationale for key changes. *The European Respiratory Journal*, 59(1). <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.02730-2021>

Research Electronic Data Capture [REDCap], (n.d) <https://projectredcap.org/>

Saelens, B. E., Glanz, K., Frank, L. D., Couch, S. C., Zhou, C., Colburn, T., & Sallis, J. F. (2018). Two-year changes in child weight status, diet, and activity by neighborhood nutrition and physical activity environment: Neighborhood and child weight status change. *Obesity* 26(8), 1338–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1002/oby.22247>

- Sanz-Santiago, V., Diez-Vega, I., Santana-Sosa, E., Lopez Nuevo, C., Iturriaga Ramirez, T., Vendrusculo, F. M., Donadio, M. V. F., Villa Asensi, J. R., & Pérez-Ruiz, M. (2020). Effect of a combined exercise program on physical fitness, lung function, and quality of life in patients with controlled asthma and exercise symptoms: A randomized controlled trial. *Pediatric Pulmonology*, *55*(7), 1608–1616. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppul.24798>
- Schneider, D., & Panton, J. (2024). Diagnostic evaluation and management of pediatric obesity in primary care. *Advances in Family Practice Nursing*, *6*(1) 235-254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yfnp.2024.01.016>
- Schroeder, K., Schuler, B. R., Kobulsky, J. M., & Sarwer, D. B. (2021). The association between adverse childhood experiences and childhood obesity: A systematic review. *Obesity Reviews*, *22*(7). <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.13204>
- Shan, L.S., Zhou, Q.L., & Shang, Y. X. (2020). Bidirectional association between asthma and obesity during childhood and adolescence: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Pediatrics*, *(8)* 576858–576858. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fped.2020.576858>
- Shaw, M. R., Katz, J., Benavides-Vaello, S., Oneal, G., & Holliday, C. (2017). Views on exercise: A grounded theory exploration of the creation of exercise perceptions in Hispanic children with asthma. *Hispanic Health Care International*, *15*(2), 71–78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1540415317707915>
- State of California, Public Utilities Commission. (2024). *Disadvantaged communities*. www.cpuc.ca.gov
- State of California, Department of Health Care Services. (2024a). *Did you know? Being physically active can prevent and manage stress*. State of California.

<https://www.acesaware.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/UCAANACEsAwareStressBustersPhysicallyActive062023.pdf>

State of California Department of Health Care Services. (2024b). *Stress busters: seven ways to manage stress*. State of California. <https://www.acesaware.org/managestress/>

State of California Department of Health Care Services. (2024c). *The science of ACES & toxic stress*. State of California. <https://www.acesaware.org/ace-fundamentals/the-science-of-aces-toxic-stress/>

State of California Department of Health Care Services. (2024d). *Trauma-informed care*. State of California. <https://www.acesaware.org/ace-fundamentals/principles-of-trauma-informed-care/>

Stierman, B., Afful, J., Carroll, M. D., Chen, T., Davy, O., Fink, S., Fryar, C. D., Gu, Q., Hales, C. M., Hughes, J. P., Ostchega, Y., Storandt, R. J., Akinbami, L. J. (2021). National health and nutrition examination survey 2017–March 2020 prepandemic data files development of files and prevalence estimates for selected health outcomes. *National Center for Health Statistics No 158*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15620/cdc:106273>

Stratakis, N., Garcia, E., Chandran, A., Hsu, T., Alshawabkeh, A., Aris, I. M., Aschner, J. L., Breton, C., Burbank, A., Camargo, C. A., Jr, Carroll, K. N., Chen, Z., Claud, E. C., Dabelea, D., Dunlop, A. L., Elliott, A. J., Ferrara, A., Ganiban, J. M., Gern, J. E., Gold, D. R., ... program collaborators for Environmental Influences on Child Health Outcomes (2022). The role of childhood asthma in obesity development: A nationwide U.S. multicohort study. *Epidemiology*, 33(1), 131–140.

<https://doi.org/10.1097/EDE.0000000000001421>

Swann, C., Jackman, P. C., Lawrence, A., Hawkins, R. M., Goddard, S. G., Williamson, O., Schweickle, M. J., Vella, S. A., Rosenbaum, S., & Ekkekakis, P. (2023). The (over)use of smart goals for physical activity promotion: A narrative review and critique. *Health Psychology Review*, 17(2), 211–226. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17437199.2021.2023608>

The Community Preventive Services Task Force. (2017). *Physical activity: family-based interventions*. The Community Guide. <https://www.thecommunityguide.org/findings/physical-activity-family-based-interventions.html>

Tran, T. N., MacLachlan, S., Hicks, W., Liu, J., Chung, Y., Zangrilli, J., Rubino, A., & Ganz, M. L. (2021). Oral corticosteroid treatment patterns of patients in the United States with persistent asthma. *The Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology in Practice*, 9(1), 338-346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaip.2020.06.019>

U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. (2018). *Physical activity guidelines for Americans*. 2nd ed. Washington, DC: U.S. Dept of Health and Human Services https://health.gov/sites/default/files/201909/PhysicalActivityGuidelines_2nd_edition.pdf

U.S. Department of Health and Human Service. (n.d.-a). *Overweight and obesity*. Healthy People 2030. <https://health.gov/healthypeople/objectives-and-data/browse-objectives/overweight-and-obesity/reduce-proportion-children-and-adolescents-obesity-nws-04>

U.S. Department of Health and Human Service. (n.d.-b). *Reduce emergency department visits for children under 5 years with asthma – RD-02*. Healthy People 2030. <https://health.gov/healthypeople/objectives-and-data/browse-objectives/overweight-and-obesity/reduce-proportion-children-and-adolescents-obesity-nws-04>

- U.S. Department of Health and Human Service. (n.d.-c). *Underserved group*. The National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences Toolkit for Patient Focused Therapy Development. <https://toolkit.ncats.nih.gov/glossary/underserved-group/>
- U.S. Office of Disease Prevention and Health Promotion. (2023). *Move your way community resources*. Department of Health and Human Services. <https://health.gov/our-work/nutrition-physical-activity/move-your-way-community-resources>
- Wiesenthal, E. N., Fagnano, M., Cook, S., & Halterman, J. S. (2016). Asthma and overweight/obese: Double trouble for urban children. *The Journal of Asthma*, 53(5), 485–491. <https://doi.org/10.3109/02770903.2015.1108435>
- World Health Organization. (2024). *Asthma*. <https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/asthma>
- Wu, X., Gao, S., & Lian, Y. (2020). Effects of continuous aerobic exercise on lung function and quality of life with asthma: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Thoracic Disease*, 12(9), 4781–4795. <https://doi.org/10.21037/jtd-19-2813>
- Zhang, Y., Chen, Z., Berhane, K., Urman, R., Chatzi, V. L., Breton, C., & Gilliland, F. D. (2020). The dynamic relationship between asthma and obesity in school children. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 189(6), 583–591. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwz257>

Appendix A

Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Figure 1

Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

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Appendix B

Permission to Use the Iowa Model Revised

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Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics <survey-bounce@survey.uiowa.edu>
To: Mendoza, Linda Sat 2/25/2023 3:39 PM

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Reply Forward

Appendix C

Figure 2: Adaptation of the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

Figure 2

Adaptation of the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

Appendix D

Wellness on Wheels: An NRC Health Community Insight Study (NRC, 2022)

Executive Summary

Community Wellness Needs

- 60% of respondents are very or somewhat likely to utilize a mobile outreach van for medical care (e.g., asthma, education related to obesity, mental health screening and referrals, etc.).
- When respondents were asked what services they would utilize with a mobile outreach van, the top services included mental health, physical health, vaccinations, and asthma care.
- More than half of respondents would like further support or education about mental wellness (64%), and physical wellness (59%).
- Respondents most often ranked mental wellness (39%) as the area they need the most support with for their child's or family's wellness, followed closely by physical wellness (30%).

Mobile Clinic Usage

- Around half of respondents indicated that if weekend programs (52%) and after school hours (46%) were available it would help improve their participation in programs provided by the CHOC mobile outreach van or other affiliated community partners.
- Overall, respondents are most likely to utilize the mobile clinic's services on Saturday mornings (55%). During the weekdays, respondents are most likely to use the mobile clinic's services during the afternoon (48%) or evening hours (45%).
- Most respondents (78%) would find it very or somewhat easy to get their family to a CHOC facility after receiving a referral from the CHOC mobile outreach van.

Appendix E

Recruitment Flyer

LEARN HOW EXERCISE CAN IMPROVE YOUR CHILD'S HEALTH

**Volunteers are needed to participate in a one-hour
educational class**

You May Qualify if You:

- Are the parent/guardian of a child with asthma
- Your child is a patient of Wellness on Wheels (formerly Breathmobile)
- Your child is between the ages of 6 to 11

Participation Involves:

- Filling out an anonymous survey
- A one-hour class at a community center

*Drinks and snacks
provided*

For More Information, Please Contact:
Linda Mendoza, MSN, CPNP-PC, AE-C
CHOC Wellness on Wheels (Formerly Breathmobile)
(714) 509-7571

Appendix F

IRB Exemption Letter

1201 W. La Veta Avenue
Orange, CA 92868

T 714 997 3000

W choc.org

DATE: July 31, 2023

TO: Linda Mendoza, MSN, CPNP-PC
FROM: Children's Hospital of Orange County In-House (CHOC IH) IRB

IRB #: 230574

STUDY TITLE: 230574-Family-Centered and Community-Based Education to Increase Physical Activity in Children with Asthma
PROTOCOL: 230574
SPONSOR:
STUDY STATUS: EXEMPT
IRBNET ID#: 2078622-1

ACTION: DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS
LEVEL OF REVIEW: Exempt Review
MTG/ ACTION DATE: July 25, 2023
EXPIRATION DATE: July 24, 2026

REVIEW CATEGORY: Exemption category # 2

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this study on July 11, 2023. The Children's Hospital of Orange County In-House (CHOC IH) IRB has determined this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations.

LIST OF STUDY DOCUMENTS IN THIS PACKAGE:

- Advertisement - 230574_Recruitment Flyer.docx (UPDATED: 07/19/2023)
- Application Form - 230574_Exemption Request Form.doc (UPDATED: 07/11/2023)
- Data Collection - 230574_Data Collection Instrument.pdf (UPDATED: 07/28/2023)
- Investigator Agreement - 230547_Personnel Chart.docx (UPDATED: 07/11/2023)
- Letter - 230574-NRIC Approval Form.pdf (UPDATED: 07/11/2023)
- Letter - 230574-Organizational_Letter_of_Support_for_BGCSA.docx.pdf (UPDATED: 07/11/2023)
- Other - 230574_Education Brochure- Physical Activity and Asthma.pdf (UPDATED: 07/28/2023)
- Other - 230547_Permissions for Survey Questions.pdf (UPDATED: 07/11/2023)
- Other - 230547_Education Lesson Plan and Materials.docx (UPDATED: 07/11/2023)
- Protocol - 230574_Protocol_Clean.docx (UPDATED: 07/20/2023)
- Protocol - 230574_Protocol_Track Changes.docx (UPDATED: 07/20/2023)

You may proceed with your project as presented to the IRB; The exemption determination for this study no longer carries an expiration. If you wish to continue your project beyond the 3-Year exemption period, a Study Status form and supporting documents will need to be submitted for Administrative Review. Please submit a Study Status form and supporting documents by the Next Report Due date noted on this letter. Your documentation for Administrative Review must be received with sufficient time for review by the Next Report Due date of **July 24, 2026**.

Appendix G

Project Approval Letter

Institutional Approval Letter

April 26, 2023

This letter is to show that, I, Clarisse Casilang MD as the Physician Lead of Wellness on Wheels

at CHOC Children's Hospital give permission to Linda Mendoza MSN, CPNP-PC to conduct the project titled A Family-Centered and Community-Based Educational Program Increasing Physical Activity in Children with Asthma on the following unit(s) Wellness on Wheels at CHOC Children's Hospital during the Fall 2023 and Spring 2024 semesters.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Nursing Research Council, (and/or other entities in the facility as needed) at CHOC Children's Hospital., and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to:

- 1) collect deidentified demographic data
- 2) access necessary documents/data
- 3) conduct necessary interactions with staff and participants relevant to their project
- 4) distribute and collect surveys to the participants

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at CHOC Children's Hospital., and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Signature:

Signature:

Name: Clarisse Casilang, MD

Name:

Title: Community Pediatrics Lead Physician

Title:

Contact Information:
ccasilang@choc.org
 (714) 509-7571

Contact Information:

Appendix H

Data Collection Timeline of Variables and Measures

Variable	Measure	Timeline		
		1	2	3
		Pre	Post	1 month
Demographic Characteristics	Survey (open-ended)	x		
Exercise symptoms	5- point Likert-scale	x	x	x
Physical activity	5- point Likert-scale	x	x	x
Perceptions/beliefs/knowledge	5- point Likert-scale	x	x	x
Community	5- point Likert scale	x	x	x
Goal setting	Survey- (open-ended)		x	x

Appendix I

Invitation to RedCap Survey Participation

Physical Activity in Children with Asthma

Page 1

You are invited to take part in a study conducted by Linda Mendoza, a graduate student at California State University, Los Angeles.

This survey is intended to collect information regarding physical activity engagement, understanding, and needs related to children with asthma.

Participation in this survey is optional. Your responses are anonymous and confidential. No personal information will be collected or reported.

The results will be used to determine if implementation of an educational program for parents/caregivers of school-aged children with asthma assists in increasing understanding of the importance of physical activity and participation in physical activity.

If you have any questions regarding this survey, please contact Linda Mendoza- (714) 509- 7571.

-
- 1) Please create a unique identifier by entering the last 4 digits of your cell phone followed by 2 digits representing your birth month.

(For example, if my phone number is (714) 509-9339 and I was born in April (04) then my unique identifier is 933904.)

-
- 2) When are you completing this survey?

- Before education session
 After education session
 1 Month after education session

Appendix J**Measurement Tools: Demographic Characteristics**

Demographic Characteristics
Language: English or Spanish
Parent/caregiver age
Parent/caregiver ethnicity
Parent/caregiver race
Parent/caregiver gender
Relationship to child with asthma
Age of child
of family members in household

Appendix K

Measurement Tools: Surveys

Asthma Symptoms and Physical Activity	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
My child does physical activity (after school) where their heart beats faster, and their breathing is harder than normal for 30 minutes or more per day?	1	2	3	4	5
My child is physically active for 60 minutes or more per day.	1	2	3	4	5
When my child exercises, runs, or plays sports, he or she has trouble with asthma.	1	2	3	4	5
My child needs his albuterol inhaler AFTER running, playing, or sports activities.	1	2	3	4	5
Parental Knowledge/Perceptions/Beliefs	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Physical activity is important for all children	1	2	3	4	5
Physical activity may make a child's asthma worse	1	2	3	4	5
Physical activity may make a child's asthma better	1	2	3	4	5
Exercise or sports are not safe for children with asthma	1	2	3	4	5
Children with asthma should be physically active for at least one hour per day	1	2	3	4	5
I am afraid that my child will get sick if he or she does physical activity, exercise, or sports	1	2	3	4	5
Community Assessment Needs and Barriers	Very unlikely	Unlikely	Neutral	Likely	Very Likely
There is a safe and convenient place for my child/children to get exercise or play outdoors in my neighborhood.	1	2	3	4	5
We live near a recreational/community center or park that is accessible.	1	2	3	4	5
There is not enough time in the day to find time to be physically active.	1	2	3	4	5
My child participates in sports or physical activity classes after school	1	2	3	4	5

Appendix M

One- Month Post Education Survey: Goal Setting

Goal Setting Assessment	
Was the physical activity goal for your child, created during the education session, achieved within the last month?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
If "No" was selected above, what were some contributing barriers to not achieving the physical activity goal for your child?	<input type="radio"/> Not enough time <input type="radio"/> No safe or convenient place <input type="radio"/> My child was sick <input type="radio"/> Other
If "Other" was selected above, please explain. _____	
Was the physical activity goal for your family, created during the education session, achieved within the last month?	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No
If "No" was selected above, what were some contributing barriers to not achieving the physical activity goal for your family?	<input type="radio"/> Not enough time <input type="radio"/> No safe or convenient place <input type="radio"/> A family member was sick <input type="radio"/> Other
If "Other" was selected above, please explain. _____	

Appendix N

Education Lesson Plan: The Importance of Physical Activity for Children with Asthma

Topic content	Content	Team Member	Time (60 min)
Introduction	Welcome, introductions, and objectives	P.I.	5
Understanding Asthma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Brief overview of asthma - Signs & symptoms - Triggers - Medications & chamber use - Asthma action plan - (True or False/ Myths, interactive game) 	P.I.	10
Exercise induced bronchoconstriction (EIB) exercise induced asthma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signs & symptoms - Management (use of SABA and AAP) 	P.I.	5
Physical Activity vs exercise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definitions & types - Benefits of PA for health and asthma - Recommendations/guidelines- <i>Move Your Way</i> - Incorporating PA into child's and family's daily routine - Encourage parent to be positive role models. - Encourage health lifestyle (sleep, healthy eating) 	P.I.	15
Community Resources & support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information about local community programs, classes, events, and food banks 	CRC	5
Goal Setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is goal setting? - Physical activity goal examples - Goal setting Worksheet 	P.I.	10
Summary/wrap up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Questions & Discussion 	P.I.	5

Note: P.I.- Principal Investigator, CRC- Community Resource Center staff member, SABA-

Short- acting beta antagonists (albuterol), AAP- Asthma Action Plan. Physical Activity- PA

Appendix O

Education adapted from the Wee Breathers Program of the AAFA (2013)

Wee Breathers Program (Eng-PDF)

[Close Window](#)

Photos Product Description

This program is for health professionals who teach parents of young children about managing asthma. Use it during home visits, one-on-one or in group classes for parents in child care centers. All handouts are at a sixth-grade reading level or lower. The full program includes:

- An Instructor's Guide
- An 'Asthma-Friendly Home: Checklist for Families'
- An 'Asthma-Friendly Child Care: Checklist for Providers'
- Seven lessons on asthma management that include lesson handouts (handouts are at a sixth-grade reading level or lower):
 - Lesson 1: Asthma Basics
 - Lesson 2: Asthma Triggers
 - Lesson 3: Controlling Asthma Triggers
 - Lesson 4: Asthma Medicines
 - Lesson 5: Asthma Action Plan
 - Lesson 6: Communicating with the Asthma Team
 - Lesson 7: Asthma Management Goals

The full program is available in English only. Only the lesson **handouts** are available in Spanish. [You can order the free PDF of the Spanish lesson handouts here.](#)

**Please choose a quantity of 1 when ordering a free PDF download. A link to download the PDF will be included in your receipt email sent after checkout. You will then be able to print multiple copies from that download.*

Appendix P

Move Your Way English Factsheet for Parents (ODPHP, 2023)

You know kids need physical activity to grow up strong and healthy. But did you know it can help them feel better right away?

Better sleep

Better mood

Better grades

And when your kids are feeling good, your life is easier, too. So find ways to help your kids fit more activity into their day.

How much do they need?

Kids and teens ages 6 to 17 need at least **60 minutes** every day.

Most of it can be **moderate-intensity aerobic activity**. Anything that gets their heart beating faster counts.

At least 3 days a week, encourage your kids to step it up to **vigorous-intensity aerobic activity**.

Is it moderate or vigorous? Use the "talk test" to find out.

When you're being active, try talking:

- ✓ If you're breathing hard but can still have a conversation easily, it's **moderate-intensity activity**
- ✓ If you can only say a few words before you have to take a breath, it's **vigorous-intensity activity**

As part of their daily 60 minutes, kids and teens also need:

Muscle-strengthening activity
At least 3 days a week

Anything that makes their muscles work harder counts — like climbing or swinging on the monkey bars.

Bone-strengthening activity
At least 3 days a week

Bones need pressure to get stronger. Running, jumping, and other weight-bearing activities all count.

My kids are younger than 6. What about them?

Younger kids love to be active naturally!

- Aim to keep them moving 3 hours a day — and more is better
- Limit time when they're just sitting around (like screen time)

What counts?

Whatever gets them moving!

Encourage active play with friends

Give them rewards for active chores

Sign them up for free or low-cost sports or classes

Or get active together!

Make your morning walks a race

Dance while dinner's in the oven

Show them your favorite ways to move

Most of all, help them find activities they really like to do!

It all adds up. And so do the benefits.

Help them get active now, and they'll build healthy habits for life. So take the first step. Get your kids moving. And when you can, move with them!

Find out how your kids can get 60 minutes of activity every day.
health.gov/MoveYourWay/Get-Kids-Active

Appendix Q

Move Your Way Spanish Factsheet for Parents (ODPHP, 2023)

Tú sabes que los niños necesitan la actividad física para crecer fuertes y sanos. Pero, ¿sabías que la actividad física también ofrece otros beneficios?

Mejor calidad de sueño

Mejor estado de ánimo

Mejores calificaciones

Y cuando tus hijos se sienten bien, tu vida también es más fácil. Busca formas de ayudarles a agregar más actividad física al día.

¿Cuánta actividad necesitan?

Los niños y adolescentes de entre 6 y 17 años necesitan por lo menos **60 minutos** todos los días.

La mayoría de estos minutos pueden ser de **actividad aeróbica moderada**. Todo lo que haga que el corazón lata más rápido cuenta.

Por lo menos 3 días por semana animalos a esforzarse más y a hacer **actividades aeróbicas intensas**.

¿Es moderada o intensa? Averígualo con la "prueba del habla."

Cuando estés haciendo la actividad, trata de hablar:

- ✓ Si respiras más rápido pero todavía puedes conversar fácilmente, es una **actividad moderada**.
- ✓ Si solo puedes decir unas pocas palabras antes de tomar aliento, es una **actividad intensa**.

Dentro de los 60 minutos diarios, los niños y adolescentes también necesitan:

Actividades para fortalecer los músculos por lo menos 3 días por semana

Toda actividad que haga que los músculos trabajen más que de costumbre cuenta, como trepar o colgar de las barras del patio de juegos.

Actividades para fortalecer los huesos por lo menos 3 días por semana

Los huesos necesitan presión para ser más fuertes. Las actividades como correr y saltar cuentan, así como otras en que se soporta peso.

Mis niños tienen menos de 6 años. ¿Qué hago en ese caso?

A los niños más pequeños les encanta mantenerse activos por naturaleza.

- Procura que estén en movimiento 3 horas diarias. Y más sería mejor.
- Limita el tiempo que pasen sentados (por ejemplo, frente a una pantalla).

¿Qué cuenta?

¡Cualquier cosa que los haga moverse!

Animalos a participar en juegos activos con sus amigos.

Dales premios por hacer oficios activos en la casa.

Inscríbelos en los deportes o las clases de ejercicio gratuitos o económicos.

¡O manténganse activos juntos!

Conviertan la caminata de la mañana en una carrera.

Bailen mientras la cena sale del horno.

Muéstrales tus formas favoritas de moverte.

Pero sobre todo, ayúdalos a encontrar actividades que de veras les gusten.

Todo se va sumando. Los beneficios también se suman.

Ayuda a tus hijos a mantenerse activos ahora. Así, ellos aprenderán costumbres sanas para toda la vida. Da el primer paso. Anima a tus hijos a moverse más. Y cuando puedas, ¡muévete con ellos!

Aquí encontrarás consejos para ponerte en movimiento y hacer un plan semanal de actividad física.
health.gov/MoveYourWay/Get-Kids-Active/es

Appendix R

Move Your Way Factsheet for Children in English (ODPHP, 2023)

You know how sometimes it's really, really hard to sit still?

YEP.

When you're young, your body **wants** to move — naturally! (Adults, not so much.)

So get active every day — and feel great!

Moving more can give you a boost — in lots of ways.

* It's true — physical activity can actually help you do better in school.

How much activity do I need?

If you're between age 6 and 17, you need at least **60 minutes** of activity each and every day.

So, what kind of activity do I need?

Get a mix of activity. Do things that:

Strengthen your bones

Build your muscles

Make your heart beat faster

Um, strengthen my bones?

Sounds weird, right? But bones need pressure to get stronger. So hit the ground running! Jump, sprint, or do a cartwheel.

60 minutes all at once? I'm pretty busy.

Not a problem! Split up your 60 minutes over the day however you want — it all adds up!

Before school

Walk to school or the bus stop!
Dance around the living room!

At recess

Play with your friends!
Swing on the monkey bars!

After school

Walk your dog!
Go to basketball practice!

So get moving! Do activities you enjoy!

Be a good role model for your parents. Even better, go home and get them moving, too.

Walk. Run. Dance. Play. What's your move?

Appendix S

Move Your Way Factsheets for Children in Spanish (ODPHP, 2023)

¿Has notado que a veces es muy difícil quedarte quieto en la silla?

¡Sí!

Es natural que los niños **quieran** moverse.
(A los adultos no les pasa tanto).

Mantente activo todos los días. Así te sentirás muy bien.

Moverse puede estimularte de muchas formas.

*¡Es cierto! Los niños y adolescentes activos tienen mejores calificaciones.

¿Cuánta actividad necesito?

Si tienes entre 6 y 17 años, necesitas por lo menos **60 minutos** diarios de actividad.

¿Y qué tipo de actividad necesito?

Haz una mezcla de varias actividades que:

Fortalezcan los huesos

Fortalezcan los músculos

Hagan que el corazón lata más rápido

¿Cómo?
¿Fortalecer los huesos?

Suena un poco raro, ¿no? Pero es verdad. Los huesos necesitan presión para ser más fuertes. Así que, ¡no te quedes quieto! Salta, corre o da volteretas (ruedas).

¿Los 60 minutos de una sola vez? ¡Tengo mucho que hacer!

No te preocupes. Reparte los 60 minutos a lo largo del día como quieras.
¡Todos se van sumando!

Antes de la escuela

Camina hasta la escuela o hasta la parada del autobús.

Baila en la sala.

En el recreo

Juega con tus amigos.

Haz ejercicio en las barras del equipo del patio de juegos.

Después de la escuela

Sal a caminar con el perro.

Ve al entrenamiento de basketbol.

¡Ponte en movimiento! Haz actividades que te gusten.

Dales buen ejemplo a tus padres. Y cuando llegues a casa, ¡invítalos a moverse también!

Camina. Corre. Baila. Juega. Es tu turno. Tú decides.

Appendix T

Table 1 Socio-demographic Characteristics

Table 1

Socio-demographic Characteristics

Characteristics	N	%
Age		
25-34 years	1	12.5
35-44 years	5	62.5
45-54 years	2	25
Gender		
He	1	12.5
She	7	87.5
Them	0	
Ethnicity		
Hispanic Or Latino	8	100
Non-Hispanic or Latino	0	
Race		
White	1	12.5
No Response	2	25
Preferred not to state	5	62.5
Relationship to child		
Father	1	12.5
Mother	7	87.5
Family household #		
4	2	25
5	1	12.5
6	5	62.5

Note. N=8. One participant did not complete demographic portion of survey

Appendix U

Table 2: Distribution of Asthma and Physical Activity Characteristics

Table 2

Distribution of Asthma and Physical Activity Characteristics

Characteristic	Response	Frequency	Proportion %
My child does physical activity where their heart beats faster and their breathing is harder for more than 30 minutes per day.	Always	1	12.5
	Often	1	12.5
	Rarely	1	12.5
	Sometimes	5	62.5
	Never	0	0
My child is physically active for 60 minutes or more per day.	Always	0	0
	Often	5	62.5
	Rarely	1	12.5
	Sometimes	1	12.5
	Never	1	12.5
When my child exercises, runs, or plays sports he or she has trouble with asthma.	Always	0	0
	Often	2	25
	Rarely	1	12.5
	Sometimes	4	50
	Never	1	12.5
My child needs their albuterol inhaler AFTER running playing or sports activities.	Always	0	0
	Often	2	25
	Rarely	1	12.5
	Sometimes	3	37.5
	Never	2	25
In the last 12 months have you brought your child to the emergency room for asthma symptoms?	Yes	3	37.5
	No	5	62.5
In the last 12 months has your child received a course of oral steroid medication due to breathing problems?	Yes	5	62.5
	No	3	37.5

Note. N=8. 1 participant did not answer this portion of the pre- education survey.

Appendix V

Table 3: Distribution of Likert Survey Response Stratified by Time Period

Table 3

Distribution of Likert Survey Response Stratified by Time Period

Survey Component	Pre	Post	<i>p</i>
	<i>M Mdn, SD</i>	<i>M, Mdn, SD</i>	
1. Physical activity is important for all children.	4.5,4.5,.5	4.3,5,1.3	0.69
2. Physical activity may make a child's asthma worse.	3,3.5,1.1	2.7,2,1.3	0.72
3. Exercise of sports are not safe for children with asthma.	2.2,2,1.0	2.3,2,1.3	0.95
4. Children with asthma should be physically active.	4.1,4,.64	4.5,5,.5	0.42
5. I am afraid my child will get sick if he or she does physical activity (exercise or sports).	3.1,3.5,1.1	2.7,3,1.3	0.58
6. There is a safe and convenient place for my child to get exercise.	3.7,4,.7	4,4, N.A.*	1
7. There is not enough time in the day to be physically active.	3.2,4,1.0	2.4,2,.8	0.11

Note. Statements 1-4: *N* = 8, Statements 5-7: *N* 9, *M*=mean, *Mdn*=median, *SD*= standard deviation, *N.A.*= not available, *p*<0.05, *Standard deviation could not be calculated due to missingness within variable.

Appendix W

Table 4: Physical Activity May Make a Child's Asthma Better

Table 4

Physical Activity May Make A Child's Asthma Better

Participant	Pre	Post
1	Agree	Agree
2	Agree	Agree
3	Agree	Strongly Agree
4	Undecided	Strongly Agree
5	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
6	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
7	Undecided	Strongly Agree
8	Undecided	Agree
9	Agree	*

Note. N = 9. Participants completed a 5-point Likert scale survey to “strongly disagree.” *Participant 9 did not complete a post test.

Appendix X

Table 5: I Am Afraid That My Child Will Get Sick If He Or She Does Physical Activity

Table 5

I Am Afraid That My Child Will Get Sick If He or She Does Physical Activity

Participant	Pre	Post
1	Agree	Undecided
2	Agree	Agree
3	Agree	Strongly Agree
4	Undecided	Disagree
5	Undecided	Strongly Disagree
6	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
7	Agree	Disagree
8	Agree	Disagree
9	Strongly Disagree	*

Note. $N = 9$. Participants completed a 5-point Likert scale survey to “strongly disagree.” *Participant 9 did not complete a post test.

Appendix Y

Table 6: There Is Not Enough Time in The Day for Physical Activity

Table 6

There Is Not Enough Time In The Day for Physical Activity

Participant	Pre	Post
1	Agree	Disagree
2	Disagree	Disagree
3	Disagree	Agree
4	Agree	Disagree
5	Agree	Agree
6	Disagree	Disagree
7	Disagree	Disagree
8	Agree	Disagree
9	Agree	*

Note. $N = 9$. Participants completed a 5-point Likert scale survey to “strongly disagree.” *Participant 9 did not complete a post test.

Appendix Z

Physical Activity Stress Busters Factsheet (DHCS, 2024a).

DID YOU KNOW?

Being Physically Active Can Prevent and Manage Stress

Physical activity gives us energy and increases the production of endorphins, which make us feel good. It also helps calm our brain and body when stressful things happen in our life.

It can be hard to find time in our busy lives to be physically active, but even walking, taking the stairs, and stretching at your home or workplace can help.

Check out the strategies below and see which ones might work best for you and the people you care about.

Talk to a doctor about how to exercise safely if you or the people you support have a health condition or injury.

Everyday Practices

Here are some easy ways to get physical activity to help prevent and lower stress:

- Be kind to yourself. It can be hard to find time to exercise, but you can do it.
- Make a plan and set goals for getting more physical activity. For example, start with two days per week and do different activities on each day.
- Aim to get 30 – 60 minutes of physical activity at least three times every week, but...

! Physical activity doesn't have to be a full "workout."

Take 5- to 15-minute breaks at school, work, and home throughout the day to:

- Take the stairs
- Take a walk down the hall and back
- Do 25 jumping jacks
- Pick up two water bottles and use them as weights for 10 minutes
- Stretch
- Play with your children
- Have a dance party
- Take a walk outside or at a park – meet up with friends or family to make it more fun.
- Do hopscotch or jump rope
- Go to a playground
- Ride a bike
- Join an activity or team at school or in your community, such as for sports or dance

BEING ACTIVE CAN PREVENT AND LOWER STRESS

Sometimes We Need a Little Extra Support

If you are feeling overwhelmed, these things can help:

- See if your local community center or neighborhood family center has classes or activities, such as dance, martial arts or yoga.
- Partner with a friend or family member to be physically active together.
- Use a phone app with reminders and encouragement.

Make it fun. Identify the type(s) of activities that you like.

- Walk in nature
- Dance
- Play a sport with friends, like soccer or basketball
- Do free, online exercise videos (e.g., on YouTube)
- Run
- Swim

Short activity breaks (even 2-5 minutes) can help your body process all that extra stress energy.

Do 10 jumping jacks, take a stroll around the block, or just wiggle and shake right where you are.

Sometimes We Need a Lot of Extra Support

When you are going through an extra tough time, these things can help:

- Activities that combine physical activity with breathing techniques, such as martial arts and yoga
- Support groups
- Exercise groups in your community
- Clinic-based exercise programs
- Weight management programs that combine mental health therapy with physical activity and nutrition guidance.
Ask your health care provider or your local community center about these programs.

ACES AWARE
SCREEN. TREAT. HEAL.

FOR MORE WAYS TO MANAGE STRESS:

Visit [ACESAware.org/ManageStress](https://www.ACESAware.org/ManageStress) or
Talk to your health care provider

